

Copyoftentacle01_householdv03 (english)

Variable Name	Question Text	Saved Value				
start	Hidden from user	Timestamp of form open				
end	Hidden from user	Timestamp of form save				
today	Hidden from user	Today's date				
deviceid	Hidden from user	Device ID (IMEI, Wi-Fi MAC, Android ID)				
authuser	Hidden from user	Username on device				
qd	Hidden from user					
qdate_sys	Today's Date	User selected date				
qdate_sys_isok	Is the date correct?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
qdate_e1	What is the today's date?	User selected date				
note_qd1	You have previously indicated that the system date is incorrect. The date you entered instead is the same as the system date. Please go back and either enter the correct date or indicate that the system date is correct.	User entered text				
qdate_e2	Please confirm today's date.	User selected date				
note_qd2	The dates you entered do not match. Please go back and enter and/or confirm the correct date.	User entered text				
current_year	Hidden from user					
visit_date	Hidden from user					
contacthouse	A. Is the household located in peri-urban Blantyre or the Chikwawa study sites?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Blantyre</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Chikwawa</td> </tr> </table>	1	Blantyre	2	Chikwawa
1	Blantyre					
2	Chikwawa					
grpSectionB	Hidden from user					
generated_table_list_label_18	INCLUSION CRITERIA Household Contact	User entered text				
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_19		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
contactlength	B. Has at least one Household member slept in the house for at least 7 of the last 14 nights prior to enrollment?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
contactconsent	C. Is a Household member able to provide consent for humans, animals and the environment to be sampled during the study?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes		
1	Yes					

		0	No
contactanimal	D. Does the household include at least one domestic animal, poultry or livestock animal which is fed or taken to grazing areas by a household member or resides overnight within the household perimeter?	1	Yes
		0	No
contactcap	E. Does an adult household member have capacity to provide informed consent or is a representative able to do so?	1	Yes
		0	No
contactlang	F. Does a household member speak English or Chichewa?	1	Yes
		0	No
elig	Hidden from user		
grpEligible	Hidden from user		
generated_note_name_27	The participant is eligible please proceed	User entered text	
generated_note_name_28	The participant is not eligible	User entered text	
infconsHHH	Has informed consent for the study been given by the Head of the Household?	1	Yes
		0	No
grpConsent	Hidden from user		
grpSectionC	Hidden from user		
hid_scan	Scan household ID	User captured barcode	
grpHID	Hidden from user		
hid_fail	Why were you unable to scan household ID	1	Technical error (wrong value scanned)
		2	Dirty (unscannable) barcode sticker.
		3	No barcode sticker; hand written ID
hid_e	Enter the household ID.	User entered text	
hid	Hidden from user		
hid_valid	Hidden from user		
hid_enrolled	Hidden from user		
luvisit	Hidden from user		
generated_note_name_41	`\${0}` is NOT a valid HouseHold ID. Please go back and scan or enter a valid Household ID.	User entered text	

visit	What visit is this?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>1 Month</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>3 Months</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>6 Months</td> </tr> </table>	1	1 Month	2	3 Months	3	6 Months						
1	1 Month													
2	3 Months													
3	6 Months													
generated_note_name_43	The household is not scheduled for this visit. Please navigate back and choose a valid visit or contact data department.	User entered text												
rn	Hidden from user													
repfirstname	Household representative first name (s)	User entered text												
repsurname	Household representative family name	User entered text												
repsex	Sex	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Male</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>Female</td> </tr> </table>	1	Male	0	Female								
1	Male													
0	Female													
reg	Hidden from user													
repreligion	Religion	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Christian</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Muslim</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Hindu</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Buddhist</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>No religion</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	Christian	2	Muslim	3	Hindu	4	Buddhist	5	No religion	9	Other
1	Christian													
2	Muslim													
3	Hindu													
4	Buddhist													
5	No religion													
9	Other													
has_phone	Do you have a phone number on which we can contact you?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No								
1	Yes													
0	No													
ph	Hidden from user													
ptphone1	Contact phone 1	User entered text												
phone1owner	Phone 1 owner	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Self</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Spouse/Partner</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Other family Member</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Neighbour</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	Self	2	Spouse/Partner	3	Other family Member	4	Neighbour	9	Other		
1	Self													
2	Spouse/Partner													
3	Other family Member													
4	Neighbour													
9	Other													
ptphone2	Contact phone 2	User entered text												
phone2owner	Phone 2 owner	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Self</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Spouse/Partner</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Other family Member</td> </tr> </table>	1	Self	2	Spouse/Partner	3	Other family Member						
1	Self													
2	Spouse/Partner													
3	Other family Member													

		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Neighbour</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	4	Neighbour	9	Other												
4	Neighbour																	
9	Other																	
ptphone3	Contact phone 3	User entered text																
phone3owner	Phone 3 owner	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Self</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Spouse/Partner</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Other family Member</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Neighbour</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	Self	2	Spouse/Partner	3	Other family Member	4	Neighbour	9	Other						
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2	Spouse/Partner																	
3	Other family Member																	
4	Neighbour																	
9	Other																	
grpHouseMembers	Hidden from user																	
hh0head	What is your relationship to the head of the household?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Parent</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Grandparent</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Child</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Sibling</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Spouse</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>Self</td> </tr> <tr> <td>99</td> <td>Other relative</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>Non relative</td> </tr> </table>	1	Parent	2	Grandparent	3	Child	4	Sibling	5	Spouse	6	Self	99	Other relative	7	Non relative
1	Parent																	
2	Grandparent																	
3	Child																	
4	Sibling																	
5	Spouse																	
6	Self																	
99	Other relative																	
7	Non relative																	
grpHouseHoldMembers	Hidden from user																	
hh0femad714	How many female adult HH members? (Females over 18 years of age)	User entered integer																
hh0maad714	How many male adult HH members?(Males over 18 years of age)	User entered integer																
hh0femchi714	How many female child HH members? (Females under 18 years of age)	User entered integer																
hh0malchi714	How many male child HH members? (Males under 18 years of age)	User entered integer																
adultmembers	Hidden from user																	
childmembers	Hidden from user																	
hh0ad714	Can you confirm that \${1} adults (>18 years old) members of the HH slept in house for 7 out of the last 14 nights	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No												
1	Yes																	
0	No																	
hh0ad714num	How many adults slept in the house for 7 out of the last 14 nights	User entered integer																
hh0chi714	Can you confirm that \${2} child (>18 years old) members of the																	

	HH slept in house for 7 out of the last 14 nights	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No														
1	Yes																			
0	No																			
hh0chi714num	How many child members slept in the house for 7 out of the last 14 nights	User entered integer																		
hh0vis_yn	Have you had any visitors sleeping in the house who do not normally stay with you, in the last one month	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No														
1	Yes																			
0	No																			
hh0sal	How many people in your household receive a regular salary?	User entered integer																		
hincome	What is the main source of income for the household?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>crop farming</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>cattle keeping</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>pig keeping</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>small ruminant keeping</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>poultry keeping</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>salaried employment</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>casual labouring</td> </tr> <tr> <td>8</td> <td>self-employed (Business)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>99</td> <td>other</td> </tr> </table>	1	crop farming	2	cattle keeping	3	pig keeping	4	small ruminant keeping	5	poultry keeping	6	salaried employment	7	casual labouring	8	self-employed (Business)	99	other
1	crop farming																			
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5	poultry keeping																			
6	salaried employment																			
7	casual labouring																			
8	self-employed (Business)																			
99	other																			
hincomeo	Please specify other	User entered text																		
hiredhelp	Do you have hired workers on the farm (in this case will be to look after your animals)	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Family members only</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No	3	Family members only												
1	Yes																			
0	No																			
3	Family members only																			
grpHHItems	Hidden from user																			
generated_note_name_82	Does anyone in your household own any of the following?	User entered text																		
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_83		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No														
1	Yes																			
0	No																			
car	Car/truck/motorbike	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No														
1	Yes																			
0	No																			
radio	Radio	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No														
1	Yes																			
0	No																			

cphone	Cell phone	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No						
1	Yes											
0	No											
tv	Television	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No						
1	Yes											
0	No											
bicycle	Bicycle	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No						
1	Yes											
0	No											
frig	Refrigerator	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No						
1	Yes											
0	No											
bed	Bed	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No						
1	Yes											
0	No											
hh0foodprob	During the past month how often have you had problems getting the food you need for your household?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Never</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Sometimes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Often</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Always</td> </tr> </table>	1	Never	2	Sometimes	3	Often	4	Always		
1	Never											
2	Sometimes											
3	Often											
4	Always											
hh0foodmissed	In the last 2 weeks, has an adult in your household skipped a meal or eaten less in order for there to be enough food?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Never</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Sometimes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Often</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Always</td> </tr> </table>	1	Never	2	Sometimes	3	Often	4	Always		
1	Never											
2	Sometimes											
3	Often											
4	Always											
hh0elec	Do you have electricity at home?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No						
1	Yes											
0	No											
hh0rooms	How many rooms are in your house?	User entered integer										
hh0housewalls	What are the walls in your house made of?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Unbaked bricks</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Baked bricks</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Unbaked mud</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Baked mud</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	1	Unbaked bricks	2	Baked bricks	3	Unbaked mud	4	Baked mud		
1	Unbaked bricks											
2	Baked bricks											
3	Unbaked mud											
4	Baked mud											

		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Cement</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	5	Cement	9	Other										
5	Cement															
9	Other															
hh0housewalls_other	Specify other type of walls	User entered text														
hh0housefloor	What is the floor in your house made of?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Cement</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Tile</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Carpet</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Wood</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Sand</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	Cement	2	Tile	3	Carpet	4	Wood	5	Sand	6	Other		
1	Cement															
2	Tile															
3	Carpet															
4	Wood															
5	Sand															
6	Other															
hh0housefloor_other	Specify other type of floor	User entered text														
hh0houserroof	What is the roof in your house made of?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Metal</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Thatch</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Sod</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Rustic mat</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Palm/bamboo</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	Metal	2	Thatch	3	Sod	4	Rustic mat	5	Palm/bamboo	6	Other		
1	Metal															
2	Thatch															
3	Sod															
4	Rustic mat															
5	Palm/bamboo															
6	Other															
hh0houserroof_other	Specify other type of roof	User entered text														
hh0fuelsource	What is the main source of fuel you use for cooking at home?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Electricity</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Gas (any type)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Kerosone</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Charcoal</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Coal</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>Wood</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	Electricity	2	Gas (any type)	3	Kerosone	4	Charcoal	5	Coal	6	Wood	7	Other
1	Electricity															
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3	Kerosone															
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5	Coal															
6	Wood															
7	Other															
hh0fuelsourcet	Specify other source of fuel for cooking	User entered text														
hh0toilettype	What kind of toilet facility do members of your household normally use?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Flush Toliet (any type)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Pit latrine with slab +/- foot rest</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Pit latrine with slab and cover +/- foot rest</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Pit latrine without slab/open pit</td> </tr> </table>	1	Flush Toliet (any type)	2	Pit latrine with slab +/- foot rest	3	Pit latrine with slab and cover +/- foot rest	4	Pit latrine without slab/open pit						
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		<table border="1"> <tr><td>5</td><td>Hanging toilet/latrine</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Composting toilet</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>Bucket</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>No toilet</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	5	Hanging toilet/latrine	6	Composting toilet	7	Bucket	8	No toilet	9	Other
5	Hanging toilet/latrine											
6	Composting toilet											
7	Bucket											
8	No toilet											
9	Other											
hh0toilettypet	specify other type of toilet	User entered text										
hh0toiletshare_yn	Do you share this toilet with others who are not members of your household but who live in surrounding houses?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No						
1	Yes											
0	No											
hh0toiletsharewho	How many households do you share the toilet with?	User entered integer										
hh0disptoicook	Do you dispose of waste water (eg from cooking) differently from waste from the toilet?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No						
1	Yes											
0	No											
hh0disptoicookwhere	Where do you dispose of the waste water?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Into river</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Into ground</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Onto rubbish heap</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Outside compound</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Into river	2	Into ground	3	Onto rubbish heap	4	Outside compound	5	Other
1	Into river											
2	Into ground											
3	Onto rubbish heap											
4	Outside compound											
5	Other											
hh0disptoicookwheret	Please specify other	User entered text										
hh0urfaediff	Do you dispose of human urine and faecal material differently?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No						
1	Yes											
0	No											
hh0howurhum	How do you dispose of human urine?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Into river</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Into ground</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Onto rubbish heap</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Outside compound</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Into river	2	Into ground	3	Onto rubbish heap	4	Outside compound	5	Other
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4	Outside compound											
5	Other											
hh0howurhumt	Please specify other	User entered text										
hh0whereurhum	Where do you dispose of human faecal material?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Into river</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Into ground</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Onto rubbish heap</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Outside compound</td></tr> </table>	1	Into river	2	Into ground	3	Onto rubbish heap	4	Outside compound		
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2	Into ground											
3	Onto rubbish heap											
4	Outside compound											

		5 Other																				
hh0whereurhumt	Please specify other	User entered text																				
hh0watersourcedrinking	What is the main source of drinking water for members of your household?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Bottled</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Piped into dwelling</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Piped outside dwelling</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Public tap/standpipe</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Tube well/borehole</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Tube well with powered pump</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>Cart with small tank/drum</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>Unprotected well/spring</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>Surface water (including rainwater collection)</td></tr> <tr><td>99</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Bottled	2	Piped into dwelling	3	Piped outside dwelling	4	Public tap/standpipe	5	Tube well/borehole	6	Tube well with powered pump	7	Cart with small tank/drum	8	Unprotected well/spring	9	Surface water (including rainwater collection)	99	Other
1	Bottled																					
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7	Cart with small tank/drum																					
8	Unprotected well/spring																					
9	Surface water (including rainwater collection)																					
99	Other																					
hh0watersourcedrinking_other	What other source of drinking water	User entered text																				
hh0watertime	How long does it take you to access your drinking water source?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>On premises</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>less than 30 Mins</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>more than 30 Mins</td></tr> </table>	1	On premises	2	less than 30 Mins	3	more than 30 Mins														
1	On premises																					
2	less than 30 Mins																					
3	more than 30 Mins																					
hh0watertreated	Do you treat your drinking water in any way at home?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Boiled</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Filtered</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Chlorinated</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Water already treated</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>None</td></tr> </table>	1	Boiled	2	Filtered	3	Chlorinated	5	Water already treated	4	None										
1	Boiled																					
2	Filtered																					
3	Chlorinated																					
5	Water already treated																					
4	None																					
hh0waterstore	Is water for drinking stored on the premises?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No																
1	Yes																					
0	No																					
wsore	Hidden from user																					
generated_table_list_label_120	How is it stored	User entered text																				
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_121		<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td></td><td></td></tr> </table>	1	Yes																		
1	Yes																					

		0	No
bu	Bucket	1	Yes
		0	No
jerc	Jerrycan	1	Yes
		0	No
ta	Tank	1	Yes
		0	No
jar	Jar	1	Yes
		0	No
dru	Drum	1	Yes
		0	No
bot	Bottled	1	Yes
		0	No
othws	Other	1	Yes
		0	No
hh0waterstoreother	Other water storage	User entered text	
hh0watercleaning_yn	Is the water source you use for washing/cleaning different from drinking water source?	1	Yes
		0	No
hh0watercleaningsource	What is the main source of water for cleaning and washing?	1	Bottled
		2	Piped into dwelling
		3	Piped outside dwelling
		4	Public tap/standpipe
		5	Tube well/borehole
		6	Tube well with powered pump
		7	Cart with small

		<table border="1"> <tr> <td></td> <td>tank/drum</td> </tr> <tr> <td>8</td> <td>Unprotected well/spring</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>Surface water (including rainwater collection)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>99</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>		tank/drum	8	Unprotected well/spring	9	Surface water (including rainwater collection)	99	Other
	tank/drum									
8	Unprotected well/spring									
9	Surface water (including rainwater collection)									
99	Other									
hh0watercleaningsourcet	Please specify other	User entered text								
hh0watercleaningtime	How long does it take to access the water you use for washing and cleaning?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>On premises</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>less than 30 Mins</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>more than 30 Mins</td> </tr> </table>	1	On premises	2	less than 30 Mins	3	more than 30 Mins		
1	On premises									
2	less than 30 Mins									
3	more than 30 Mins									
grpSectionF	Hidden from user									
grpAntibioticsAdult	Hidden from user									
generated_note_name_137	If a member of the household needs antibiotics where do you normally get them from?	User entered text								
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_138		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No				
1	Yes									
0	No									
hosp_gov	Hospital (gov)	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No				
1	Yes									
0	No									
hosp_pvt	Hospital (private)	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No				
1	Yes									
0	No									
hosp_othclin	Other clinic (gov)	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No				
1	Yes									
0	No									
hosp_pham	Otherpharmacy (gov)	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No				
1	Yes									
0	No									
hosp_shop	Shop/market	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No				
1	Yes									
0	No									
hosp_trad	Traditional medical practitioner	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes						
1	Yes									

		0	No
hosp_friend	Friend/family	1	Yes
		0	No
hosp_othr	Other	1	Yes
		0	No
hosp_otprt	Please specify where you would normally get antibiotics	User entered text	
whabx	Hidden from user		
generated_note_name_149	Why do you choose to get antibiotics from here?	User entered text	
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_150		1	Yes
		0	No
hcuabxwhy1	Cost	1	Yes
		0	No
hcuabxwhy2	Location	1	Yes
		0	No
hcuabxwhy3	Availability of drugs	1	Yes
		0	No
hcuabxwhy4	Recommended by doctor	1	Yes
		0	No
hcuabxwhy9	Other	1	Yes
		0	No
hcuabxwhy9t	Please specify other reason	User entered text	
hcuadfac	Where do members of the household normally seek healthcare in case of illness?	1	Hospital (gov)
		2	Hospital (private)
		3	Other clinic (gov)
		4	Private facility
		5	Traditional medical

		<table border="1"> <tr> <td></td> <td>practitioner</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>Friend/family</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>CHAM facility</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>		practitioner	6	Friend/family	7	CHAM facility	9	Other										
	practitioner																			
6	Friend/family																			
7	CHAM facility																			
9	Other																			
hcuadfac0	Please specify other place where the household normally seeks care	User entered text																		
hcuabwhyad	What is the name of the facility	User entered text																		
hh0diarrhoeanow	Does anyone in the household have diarrhoea at the moment?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No														
1	Yes																			
0	No																			
hh0diarrhomany	How many people in the house have diarrhoea at the moment?	User entered integer																		
hcudiarrhoea	Have there been any cases of diarrhoeal disease in the household during the past 3 months?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No														
1	Yes																			
0	No																			
hcudiarrhoeawhead	Where do members of the household normally seek healthcare in case of diarrhoea?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>QECH</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Other hospital (gov)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Health centre (gov)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Pharmacy (gov)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Private facility</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>Traditional medical practitioner</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>Friend/family</td> </tr> <tr> <td>8</td> <td>CHAM facility</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	QECH	2	Other hospital (gov)	3	Health centre (gov)	4	Pharmacy (gov)	5	Private facility	6	Traditional medical practitioner	7	Friend/family	8	CHAM facility	9	Other
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7	Friend/family																			
8	CHAM facility																			
9	Other																			
hcudiarrhoeawheadt	Please specify other	User entered text																		
hh0fevernow	Does anyone in the household have a fever at the moment?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No														
1	Yes																			
0	No																			
hh0feverwho	How many people in the house have fever at the moment?	User entered integer																		
hcufever	Have there been any cases of febrile illness in the household during the past 3 months?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No														
1	Yes																			
0	No																			
hcufeverwhead	Where do members of the household normally seek healthcare in case of fever?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>QECH</td> </tr> </table>	1	QECH																
1	QECH																			

		<table border="1"> <tr><td>2</td><td>Other hospital (gov)</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Health centre (gov)</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Pharmacy (gov)</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Private facility</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Traditional medical practitioner</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>Friend/family</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>CHAM facility</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	2	Other hospital (gov)	3	Health centre (gov)	4	Pharmacy (gov)	5	Private facility	6	Traditional medical practitioner	7	Friend/family	8	CHAM facility	9	Other
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6	Traditional medical practitioner																	
7	Friend/family																	
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9	Other																	
hcufeverwheadt	Please specify other	User entered text																
grpSectionG	Hidden from user																	
grpFoodfrequency	Hidden from user																	
generated_note_name_173	How often do household members eat the following:	User entered text																
hh0foodbeef	Beef	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Never</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Less than once a week</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>About once a week</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Several times a week</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Daily</td></tr> </table>	1	Never	2	Less than once a week	3	About once a week	4	Several times a week	5	Daily						
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5	Daily																	
hh0foodpork	Pork	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Never</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Less than once a week</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>About once a week</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Several times a week</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Daily</td></tr> </table>	1	Never	2	Less than once a week	3	About once a week	4	Several times a week	5	Daily						
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2	Less than once a week																	
3	About once a week																	
4	Several times a week																	
5	Daily																	
hh0foodgoat	Goat	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Never</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Less than once a week</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>About once a week</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Several times a week</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Daily</td></tr> </table>	1	Never	2	Less than once a week	3	About once a week	4	Several times a week	5	Daily						
1	Never																	
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5	Daily																	
hh0foodchi	Chicken	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Never</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Less than once a week</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>About once a week</td></tr> <tr><td></td><td></td></tr> </table>	1	Never	2	Less than once a week	3	About once a week										
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		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Several times a week</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Daily</td> </tr> </table>	4	Several times a week	5	Daily								
4	Several times a week													
5	Daily													
hh0foodoth	Other meat	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Never</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Less than once a week</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>About once a week</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Several times a week</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Daily</td> </tr> </table>	1	Never	2	Less than once a week	3	About once a week	4	Several times a week	5	Daily		
1	Never													
2	Less than once a week													
3	About once a week													
4	Several times a week													
5	Daily													
hh0othwhi	Specify name of other meat	User entered text												
hh0veggrow	Do you have land on which you grow vegetables?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No								
1	Yes													
0	No													
hh0rawvegplot	How often do household members eat salad/raw veg from own plot?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Never</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Less than once a week</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>About once a week</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Several times a week</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Daily</td> </tr> </table>	1	Never	2	Less than once a week	3	About once a week	4	Several times a week	5	Daily		
1	Never													
2	Less than once a week													
3	About once a week													
4	Several times a week													
5	Daily													
hh0rawvegmarket	How often do household members eat salad/raw veg from the market?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Never</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Less than once a week</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>About once a week</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Several times a week</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Daily</td> </tr> </table>	1	Never	2	Less than once a week	3	About once a week	4	Several times a week	5	Daily		
1	Never													
2	Less than once a week													
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4	Several times a week													
5	Daily													
hh0rawvegwhere	Which market do you get them from?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Golio Market</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Zambia Markket</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Chinseu Market</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Ndirande Market</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Makata Market</td> </tr> <tr> <td>99</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	Golio Market	2	Zambia Markket	3	Chinseu Market	4	Ndirande Market	5	Makata Market	99	Other
1	Golio Market													
2	Zambia Markket													
3	Chinseu Market													
4	Ndirande Market													
5	Makata Market													
99	Other													
hh0rawvegwhereo	Please specify market name	User entered text												
hh0fruit	Do you grow fruit on your household land?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No								
1	Yes													
0	No													

hh0fruitplot	How often do you eat fruit from own plot?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Never</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Less than once a week</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>About once a week</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Several times a week</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Daily</td></tr> </table>	1	Never	2	Less than once a week	3	About once a week	4	Several times a week	5	Daily		
1	Never													
2	Less than once a week													
3	About once a week													
4	Several times a week													
5	Daily													
hh0fruitmarket	How often do you eat fruit from the market?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Never</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Less than once a week</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>About once a week</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Several times a week</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Daily</td></tr> </table>	1	Never	2	Less than once a week	3	About once a week	4	Several times a week	5	Daily		
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hh0fruitwhere	Which market do you get them from?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Golio Market</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Zambia Markket</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Chinseu Market</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Ndirande Market</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Makata Market</td></tr> <tr><td>99</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Golio Market	2	Zambia Markket	3	Chinseu Market	4	Ndirande Market	5	Makata Market	99	Other
1	Golio Market													
2	Zambia Markket													
3	Chinseu Market													
4	Ndirande Market													
5	Makata Market													
99	Other													
hh0fruitwheret	Please specify market name	User entered text												
hh0milk	Does anyone in the household consume milk from animals?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No								
1	Yes													
0	No													
hh0milkcow	How often does your household have fresh milk from a cow?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Never</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Less than once a week</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>About once a week</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Several times a week</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Daily</td></tr> </table>	1	Never	2	Less than once a week	3	About once a week	4	Several times a week	5	Daily		
1	Never													
2	Less than once a week													
3	About once a week													
4	Several times a week													
5	Daily													
hh0milkown	Do you buy this milk or is it from your own animals?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>Bought</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>Own animals</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Both</td></tr> </table>	0	Bought	1	Own animals	2	Both						
0	Bought													
1	Own animals													
2	Both													
hhmilkpast	Do you boil or pasteurise fresh milk before drinking?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes										
1	Yes													

		0	No
hh0milksh	How often does your household have fresh milk from a sheep?	1	Never
		2	Less than once a week
		3	About once a week
		4	Several times a week
		5	Daily
hh0milkshbuy	Do you buy this milk or is it from your own animals?	0	Bought
		1	Own animals
		2	Both
hh0milkshpast	Do you boil or pasteurise fresh milk before drinking?	1	Yes
		0	No
hh0milkgoa	How often does your household have fresh milk from a goat?	1	Never
		2	Less than once a week
		3	About once a week
		4	Several times a week
		5	Daily
hh0milkgoabuy	Do you buy this milk or is it from your own animals?	0	Bought
		1	Own animals
		2	Both
hh0milkgoapast	Do you boil or pasteurise this milk before drinking?	1	Yes
		0	No
grpSectionH	Hidden from user		
grpAnimalsOwned	Hidden from user		
ani0num	How many animals of each species are owned by the household?	User entered text	
ani0numcow	Cow	User entered integer	
ani0numpig	Pig	User entered integer	
ani0numshe	Sheep	User entered integer	

ani0numgoa	Goat	User entered integer				
ani0numdog	Dog	User entered integer				
ani0numcat	Cat	User entered integer				
ani0numhor	Horse	User entered integer				
ani0numdon	Donkey	User entered integer				
ani0numbir	Chicken	User entered integer				
ani0numbirot	Do you have other species not listed above?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
grpOtherAnimalsOwned	Hidden from user					
ani0numoth1	Other (specify)	User entered text				
ani0numoth2	Other (specify)	User entered text				
ani0numoth3	Other (specify)	User entered text				
oao	Hidden from user					
ani0numothnum1	Number of \${3}	User entered integer				
ani0numothnum2	Number of \${4}	User entered integer				
ani0numothnum3	Number of \${5}	User entered integer				
wakg	Hidden from user					
hmper0cow	How many Cows spend time within the household perimeter every week?	User entered integer				
hmper0pig	How many Pigs spend time within the household perimeter every week?	User entered integer				
hmper0she	How many Sheep spend time within the household perimeter every week?	User entered integer				
hmper0goa	How many Goats spend time within the household perimeter every week?	User entered integer				
hmper0dog	How many Dogs spend time within the household perimeter every week?	User entered integer				
hmper0cat	How many Cats spend time within the household perimeter every week?	User entered integer				
hmper0hor	How many Horses spend time within the household perimeter every week?	User entered integer				
hmper0don	How many Donkeys spend time within the household perimeter every week??	User entered integer				
hmper0bir	How many Chickens spend time within the household perimeter every week?	User entered integer				
hmper1othsp	How many \${3} spend time within the household perimeter every week?	User entered integer				

hmpcr2othsp	How many \$4 spend time within the household perimeter every week?	User entered integer																
hmpcr3othsp	How many \$5 spend time within the household perimeter every week?	User entered integer																
livencome	Livestock contributes to	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>To half or more of the household's income</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>to less than half of the household's income</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>does not contribute to the household income</td> </tr> </table>	1	To half or more of the household's income	2	to less than half of the household's income	3	does not contribute to the household income										
1	To half or more of the household's income																	
2	to less than half of the household's income																	
3	does not contribute to the household income																	
wak	Hidden from user																	
where0cow	Where are the Cows kept	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>In the main house,</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>In a separate building</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Under a shelter</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>In a fence within the household boundary</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Free roaming)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>Neighbour's property</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>Free roaming</td> </tr> <tr> <td>8</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	In the main house,	2	In a separate building	3	Under a shelter	4	In a fence within the household boundary	5	Free roaming)	6	Neighbour's property	7	Free roaming	8	Other
1	In the main house,																	
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7	Free roaming																	
8	Other																	
where0pig	Where are the Pigs kept	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>In the main house,</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>In a separate building</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Under a shelter</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>In a fence within the household boundary</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Free roaming)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>Neighbour's property</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>Free roaming</td> </tr> <tr> <td>8</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	In the main house,	2	In a separate building	3	Under a shelter	4	In a fence within the household boundary	5	Free roaming)	6	Neighbour's property	7	Free roaming	8	Other
1	In the main house,																	
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8	Other																	
where0she	Where are the Sheep kept	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>In the main house,</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>In a separate building</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Under a shelter</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>In a fence within the household boundary</td> </tr> </table>	1	In the main house,	2	In a separate building	3	Under a shelter	4	In a fence within the household boundary								
1	In the main house,																	
2	In a separate building																	
3	Under a shelter																	
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		<table border="1"> <tbody> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Free roaming)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>Neighbour's property</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>Free roaming</td> </tr> <tr> <td>8</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	5	Free roaming)	6	Neighbour's property	7	Free roaming	8	Other								
5	Free roaming)																	
6	Neighbour's property																	
7	Free roaming																	
8	Other																	
where0goa	Where are the Goats kept	<table border="1"> <tbody> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>In the main house,</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>In a separate building</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Under a shelter</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>In a fence within the household boundary</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Free roaming)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>Neighbour's property</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>Free roaming</td> </tr> <tr> <td>8</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	1	In the main house,	2	In a separate building	3	Under a shelter	4	In a fence within the household boundary	5	Free roaming)	6	Neighbour's property	7	Free roaming	8	Other
1	In the main house,																	
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3	Under a shelter																	
4	In a fence within the household boundary																	
5	Free roaming)																	
6	Neighbour's property																	
7	Free roaming																	
8	Other																	
where0dog	Where are the Dogs kept	<table border="1"> <tbody> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>In the main house,</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>In a separate building</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Under a shelter</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>In a fence within the household boundary</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Free roaming)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>Neighbour's property</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>Free roaming</td> </tr> <tr> <td>8</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	1	In the main house,	2	In a separate building	3	Under a shelter	4	In a fence within the household boundary	5	Free roaming)	6	Neighbour's property	7	Free roaming	8	Other
1	In the main house,																	
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4	In a fence within the household boundary																	
5	Free roaming)																	
6	Neighbour's property																	
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8	Other																	
where0cat	Where are the Cats kept	<table border="1"> <tbody> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>In the main house,</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>In a separate building</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Under a shelter</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>In a fence within the household boundary</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Free roaming)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>Neighbour's property</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>Free roaming</td> </tr> <tr> <td>8</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	1	In the main house,	2	In a separate building	3	Under a shelter	4	In a fence within the household boundary	5	Free roaming)	6	Neighbour's property	7	Free roaming	8	Other
1	In the main house,																	
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5	Free roaming)																	
6	Neighbour's property																	
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8	Other																	
where0hor	Where are the Horses kept	<table border="1"> <tbody> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>In the main house,</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	1	In the main house,														
1	In the main house,																	

		<table border="1"> <tbody> <tr><td>2</td><td>In a separate building</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Under a shelter</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>In a fence within the household boundary</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Free roaming)</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Neighbour's property</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>Free roaming</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>Other</td></tr> </tbody> </table>	2	In a separate building	3	Under a shelter	4	In a fence within the household boundary	5	Free roaming)	6	Neighbour's property	7	Free roaming	8	Other		
2	In a separate building																	
3	Under a shelter																	
4	In a fence within the household boundary																	
5	Free roaming)																	
6	Neighbour's property																	
7	Free roaming																	
8	Other																	
where0don	Where are the Donkeys kept?	<table border="1"> <tbody> <tr><td>1</td><td>In the main house,</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>In a separate building</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Under a shelter</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>In a fence within the household boundary</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Free roaming)</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Neighbour's property</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>Free roaming</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>Other</td></tr> </tbody> </table>	1	In the main house,	2	In a separate building	3	Under a shelter	4	In a fence within the household boundary	5	Free roaming)	6	Neighbour's property	7	Free roaming	8	Other
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5	Free roaming)																	
6	Neighbour's property																	
7	Free roaming																	
8	Other																	
where0bir	Where are the Chickens kept	<table border="1"> <tbody> <tr><td>1</td><td>In the main house,</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>In a separate building</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Under a shelter</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>In a fence within the household boundary</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Free roaming)</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Neighbour's property</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>Free roaming</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>Other</td></tr> </tbody> </table>	1	In the main house,	2	In a separate building	3	Under a shelter	4	In a fence within the household boundary	5	Free roaming)	6	Neighbour's property	7	Free roaming	8	Other
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5	Free roaming)																	
6	Neighbour's property																	
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8	Other																	
where1othsp	Where are the \$3 kept	<table border="1"> <tbody> <tr><td>1</td><td>In the main house,</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>In a separate building</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Under a shelter</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>In a fence within the household boundary</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Free roaming)</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Neighbour's property</td></tr> </tbody> </table>	1	In the main house,	2	In a separate building	3	Under a shelter	4	In a fence within the household boundary	5	Free roaming)	6	Neighbour's property				
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5	Free roaming)																	
6	Neighbour's property																	

		7 Free roaming																
		8 Other																
where2othsp	Where are the \${4} kept	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>In the main house,</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>In a separate building</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Under a shelter</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>In a fence within the household boundary</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Free roaming)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>Neighbour's property</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>Free roaming</td> </tr> <tr> <td>8</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	In the main house,	2	In a separate building	3	Under a shelter	4	In a fence within the household boundary	5	Free roaming)	6	Neighbour's property	7	Free roaming	8	Other
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2	In a separate building																	
3	Under a shelter																	
4	In a fence within the household boundary																	
5	Free roaming)																	
6	Neighbour's property																	
7	Free roaming																	
8	Other																	
where3othsp	Where are the \${5} kept	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>In the main house,</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>In a separate building</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Under a shelter</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>In a fence within the household boundary</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Free roaming)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>Neighbour's property</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>Free roaming</td> </tr> <tr> <td>8</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	In the main house,	2	In a separate building	3	Under a shelter	4	In a fence within the household boundary	5	Free roaming)	6	Neighbour's property	7	Free roaming	8	Other
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2	In a separate building																	
3	Under a shelter																	
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6	Neighbour's property																	
7	Free roaming																	
8	Other																	
wako	Hidden from user																	
where0cow_othr	Specify other place where cows are kept	User entered text																
where0pig_othr	Specify other place where pigs are kept	User entered text																
where0she_othr	Specify other place where sheeps are kept	User entered text																
where0goa_othr	Specify other place where goats are kept	User entered text																
where0dog_othr	Specify other place where dogs are kept	User entered text																
where0cat_othr	Specify other place where cats are kept	User entered text																
where0hor_othr	Specify other place where horses are kept	User entered text																
where0don_othr	Specify other place where donkeys are kept	User entered text																
where0bir_othr	Specify other place where chickens are kept	User entered text																
where0oth1	Specify other place where \${3} are kept	User entered text																
where0oth2	Specify other place where \${4} are kept	User entered text																
where0oth3	Specify other place where \${5} are kept	User entered text																

grpCowPurpose	Hidden from user					
generated_table_list_label_269	What is the main purpose of keeping these cows?	User entered text				
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_270		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
purp0cowmeat	Meat	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
purp0cowhide	Hide	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
purp0cowmilk	Milk	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
purp0cowoth	Other	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
purp0cowsp	Specify other purpose for keeping cows	User entered text				
grpPigPurpose	Hidden from user					
generated_table_list_label_276	What is the main purpose of keeping these pigs?	User entered text				
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_277		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
purp0pigmeat	Meat	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
purp0pigoth	Other	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
purp0pigothsp	specify other purpose for keeping pigs	User entered text				
grpShePurpose	Hidden from user					
generated_table_list_label_281	What is the main purpose of keeping these sheep?	User entered text				
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_282		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					

purp0shemeat	Meat	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
purp0shehide	Hide	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
purp0shemilk	Milk	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
purp0sheoth	Other	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
purp0sheothsp	Specify other purpose for keeping sheep	User entered text				
grpGoaPurpose	Hidden from user					
generated_table_list_label_288	What is the main purpose of keeping these goats?	User entered text				
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_289		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
purp0goameat	Meat	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
purp0goahide	Hide	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
purp0goamilk	Milk	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
purp0goaoth	Other	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
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0	No					
purp0goaothsp	Specify other purpose for keeping goats	User entered text				
grpDogPurpose	Hidden from user					
generated_table_list_label_295	What is the main purpose of keeping these dogs?	User entered text				
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_296		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes		
1	Yes					

		0	No
purp0dogcomp	Companion	1	Yes
		0	No
purp0dogguard	Guard	1	Yes
		0	No
purp0dogoth	Other	1	Yes
		0	No
purp0dogothsp	Specify other purpose for keeping dogs	User entered text	
grpCatPurpose	Hidden from user		
generated_table_list_label_301	What is the main purpose of keeping these cats?	User entered text	
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_302		1	Yes
		0	No
purp0catcomp	Companion	1	Yes
		0	No
purp0catguard	Guard	1	Yes
		0	No
purp0catoth	Other	1	Yes
		0	No
purp0catothsp	Specify other purpose for keeping cats	User entered text	
grpHorsePurpose	Hidden from user		
generated_table_list_label_307	What is the main purpose of keeping these horses?	User entered text	
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_308		1	Yes
		0	No
purp0horwan	Working animal	1	Yes
		0	No

purp0horguard	Guard	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
purp0horoth	Other	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
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0	No					
purp0horothsp	Specify other purpose for keeping horses	User entered text				
grpDonkeyPurpose	Hidden from user					
generated_table_list_label_313	What is the main purpose of keeping these donkeys?	User entered text				
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_314		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
purp0donwan	Working animal	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
purp0donguard	Guard	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
purp0donoth	Other	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
purp0donothsp	Specify other purpose for keeping donkeys	User entered text				
grpChickenPurpose	Hidden from user					
generated_table_list_label_319	What is the main purpose of keeping these chickens?	User entered text				
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_320		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
purp0birmeat	Meat	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
purp0birfeath	Feathers	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
purp0birguard	Guard	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes		
1	Yes					

		0	No
purp0biregg	Eggs	1	Yes
		0	No
purp0biroth	Other	1	Yes
		0	No
purp0birothsp	Specify other purpose for keeping chickens	User entered text	
grpOtherSpeciesPurpose	Hidden from user		
generated_table_list_label_327	What is the main purpose of keeping these \${3}?	User entered text	
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_328		1	Yes
		0	No
		8	Not applicable
purp0othmeat	Meat	1	Yes
		0	No
		8	Not applicable
purp0othhide	Hide	1	Yes
		0	No
		8	Not applicable
purp0othmilk	Milk	1	Yes
		0	No
		8	Not applicable
purp0othcomp	Companion	1	Yes
		0	No
		8	Not applicable
purp0othfea	Feathers	1	Yes
		0	No
		8	Not applicable

purp0othoth	Other	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>Not applicable</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No	8	Not applicable
1	Yes							
0	No							
8	Not applicable							
purp0othothsp	Specify other purpose for keeping \${3}	User entered text						
grp2therSpeciesPurpose	Hidden from user							
generated_table_list_label_336	What is the main purpose of keeping these \${4}?	User entered text						
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_337		<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>Not applicable</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No	8	Not applicable
1	Yes							
0	No							
8	Not applicable							
purp2othmeat	Meat	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>Not applicable</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No	8	Not applicable
1	Yes							
0	No							
8	Not applicable							
purp2othhide	Hide	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>Not applicable</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No	8	Not applicable
1	Yes							
0	No							
8	Not applicable							
purp2othmilk	Milk	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>Not applicable</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No	8	Not applicable
1	Yes							
0	No							
8	Not applicable							
purp2othcomp	Companion	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>Not applicable</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No	8	Not applicable
1	Yes							
0	No							
8	Not applicable							
purp2othfea	Feathers	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>Not applicable</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No	8	Not applicable
1	Yes							
0	No							
8	Not applicable							
purp2othoth	Other	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>Not applicable</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No	8	Not applicable
1	Yes							
0	No							
8	Not applicable							

purp2othothsp	Specify other purpose for keeping \${4}	User entered text						
grp3therSpeciesPurpose	Hidden from user							
generated_table_list_label_345	What is the main purpose of keeping these \${5}?	User entered text						
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_346		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>8</td> <td>Not applicable</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No	8	Not applicable
1	Yes							
0	No							
8	Not applicable							
purp3othmeat	Meat	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>8</td> <td>Not applicable</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No	8	Not applicable
1	Yes							
0	No							
8	Not applicable							
purp3othhide	Hide	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>8</td> <td>Not applicable</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No	8	Not applicable
1	Yes							
0	No							
8	Not applicable							
purp3othmilk	Milk	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>8</td> <td>Not applicable</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No	8	Not applicable
1	Yes							
0	No							
8	Not applicable							
purp3othcomp	Companion	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>8</td> <td>Not applicable</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No	8	Not applicable
1	Yes							
0	No							
8	Not applicable							
purp3othfea	Feathers	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>8</td> <td>Not applicable</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No	8	Not applicable
1	Yes							
0	No							
8	Not applicable							
purp3othoth	Other	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>8</td> <td>Not applicable</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No	8	Not applicable
1	Yes							
0	No							
8	Not applicable							
purp3othothsp	Specify other purpose for keeping \${5}	User entered text						
grpHumanAnimalContact	Hidden from user							
generated_note_name_355	How much contact do human household members have with animals per week within 2 metres of any animal (including those	User entered text						

	not owned by the household members)											
an0concow	Cow	<table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>None</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>less than 1hr</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>1-5hrs</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>5-10hrs</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>more than 10hrs</td></tr> </table>	0	None	1	less than 1hr	2	1-5hrs	3	5-10hrs	4	more than 10hrs
0	None											
1	less than 1hr											
2	1-5hrs											
3	5-10hrs											
4	more than 10hrs											
an0conpig	Pig	<table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>None</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>less than 1hr</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>1-5hrs</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>5-10hrs</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>more than 10hrs</td></tr> </table>	0	None	1	less than 1hr	2	1-5hrs	3	5-10hrs	4	more than 10hrs
0	None											
1	less than 1hr											
2	1-5hrs											
3	5-10hrs											
4	more than 10hrs											
an0conshe	Sheep	<table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>None</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>less than 1hr</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>1-5hrs</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>5-10hrs</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>more than 10hrs</td></tr> </table>	0	None	1	less than 1hr	2	1-5hrs	3	5-10hrs	4	more than 10hrs
0	None											
1	less than 1hr											
2	1-5hrs											
3	5-10hrs											
4	more than 10hrs											
an0congoa	Goat	<table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>None</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>less than 1hr</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>1-5hrs</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>5-10hrs</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>more than 10hrs</td></tr> </table>	0	None	1	less than 1hr	2	1-5hrs	3	5-10hrs	4	more than 10hrs
0	None											
1	less than 1hr											
2	1-5hrs											
3	5-10hrs											
4	more than 10hrs											
an0condog	Dog	<table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>None</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>less than 1hr</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>1-5hrs</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>5-10hrs</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>more than 10hrs</td></tr> </table>	0	None	1	less than 1hr	2	1-5hrs	3	5-10hrs	4	more than 10hrs
0	None											
1	less than 1hr											
2	1-5hrs											
3	5-10hrs											
4	more than 10hrs											
an0concat	Cat	<table border="1"> <tr><td>0</td><td>None</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>less than 1hr</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>1-5hrs</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>5-10hrs</td></tr> </table>	0	None	1	less than 1hr	2	1-5hrs	3	5-10hrs		
0	None											
1	less than 1hr											
2	1-5hrs											
3	5-10hrs											

		4	more than 10hrs
an0conhor	Horse	0	None
		1	less than 1hr
		2	1-5hrs
		3	5-10hrs
		4	more than 10hrs
an0condon	Donkey	0	None
		1	less than 1hr
		2	1-5hrs
		3	5-10hrs
		4	more than 10hrs
an0conbir	Chicken	0	None
		1	less than 1hr
		2	1-5hrs
		3	5-10hrs
		4	more than 10hrs
an0conoth1	Other species	0	None
		1	less than 1hr
		2	1-5hrs
		3	5-10hrs
		4	more than 10hrs
an0conothsp	Other (specify species)	User entered text	
charh	Hidden from user		
generated_note_name_369	What are the characteristics of livestock production systems?	User entered text	
chpig	Pig	1	free range
		2	tethered
		3	housed
		9	Other
chpoultry	Poultry	1	free range

		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>housed</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	3	housed	9	Other						
3	housed											
9	Other											
chbeef	Beef	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>zero grazing</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>fenced individual farm grazing</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>communal grazing</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>pastoral</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	zero grazing	2	fenced individual farm grazing	3	communal grazing	4	pastoral	9	Other
1	zero grazing											
2	fenced individual farm grazing											
3	communal grazing											
4	pastoral											
9	Other											
chdairy	Dairy	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>zero grazing</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>fenced individual farm grazing</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>communal grazing</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>pastoral</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	zero grazing	2	fenced individual farm grazing	3	communal grazing	4	pastoral	9	Other
1	zero grazing											
2	fenced individual farm grazing											
3	communal grazing											
4	pastoral											
9	Other											
chsmallr	Small ruminants	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>zero grazing</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>fenced individual farm grazing</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>communal grazing</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>pastoral</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	zero grazing	2	fenced individual farm grazing	3	communal grazing	4	pastoral	9	Other
1	zero grazing											
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4	pastoral											
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chequine	Equines	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>zero grazing</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>fenced individual farm grazing</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>communal grazing</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>pastoral</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	zero grazing	2	fenced individual farm grazing	3	communal grazing	4	pastoral	9	Other
1	zero grazing											
2	fenced individual farm grazing											
3	communal grazing											
4	pastoral											
9	Other											
sellmilk	Do you sell milk?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No						
1	Yes											
0	No											
sellmilkyr	Do you sell milk throughout the year	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No						
1	Yes											
0	No											

selleggs	Do you sell eggs	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
selleggsyr	Do you sell eggs throughout the year?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
grpAnimalAccesToHouse	Hidden from user					
an0acc	Which of these animals have access to the inside of the house?	User entered text				
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_383		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
an0acccow	Cow	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
an0accpig	Pig	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
an0accshe	Sheep	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
an0accgoa	Goat	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
an0accdog	Dog	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
an0accat	Cat	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
an0acchor	Horse	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
an0accdon	Donkey	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes		
1	Yes					

		0	No
an0accbir	Chicken	1	Yes
		0	No
an0accoth1	#{3}	1	Yes
		0	No
an0accoth2	#{4}	1	Yes
		0	No
an0accoth3	#{5}	1	Yes
		0	No
an0hou	Hidden from user		
generated_note_name_397	Do any of the following animals which are not owned by you ever enter your household perimeter?	User entered text	
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_398		1	Yes
		0	No
an0houcow	Cow	1	Yes
		0	No
an0houpig	Pig	1	Yes
		0	No
an0houseshe	Sheep	1	Yes
		0	No
an0hougoa	Goat	1	Yes
		0	No
an0houdog	Dog	1	Yes
		0	No

an0houcat	Cat	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No										
1	Yes															
0	No															
an0houhor	Horse	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No										
1	Yes															
0	No															
an0houdon	Donkey	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No										
1	Yes															
0	No															
an0houchi	Chicken	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No										
1	Yes															
0	No															
an0houoth	Other species	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No										
1	Yes															
0	No															
an0houotho	Please specify other species	User entered text														
hoften	Hidden from user															
generated_note_name_411	Cow	User entered text														
an0houcowoft	How often does this occur?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Several times daily</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Once daily</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>2 - 3 times weekly</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Once weekly</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Once every two weeks</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>Once monthly</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>Less frequently than once monthly</td> </tr> </table>	1	Several times daily	2	Once daily	3	2 - 3 times weekly	4	Once weekly	5	Once every two weeks	6	Once monthly	7	Less frequently than once monthly
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3	2 - 3 times weekly															
4	Once weekly															
5	Once every two weeks															
6	Once monthly															
7	Less frequently than once monthly															
generated_note_name_413	Pig	User entered text														
an0houpigoft	How often does this occur?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Several times daily</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Once daily</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>2 - 3 times weekly</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Once weekly</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Once every two weeks</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>Once monthly</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>Less frequently than</td> </tr> </table>	1	Several times daily	2	Once daily	3	2 - 3 times weekly	4	Once weekly	5	Once every two weeks	6	Once monthly	7	Less frequently than
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6	Once monthly															
7	Less frequently than															

		once monthly														
generated_note_name_415	Sheep	User entered text														
an0housheoft	How often does this occur?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Several times daily</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Once daily</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>2 - 3 times weekly</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Once weekly</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Once every two weeks</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Once monthly</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>Less frequently than once monthly</td></tr> </table>	1	Several times daily	2	Once daily	3	2 - 3 times weekly	4	Once weekly	5	Once every two weeks	6	Once monthly	7	Less frequently than once monthly
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7	Less frequently than once monthly															
generated_note_name_417	Goat	User entered text														
an0hougoaft	How often does this occur?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Several times daily</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Once daily</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>2 - 3 times weekly</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Once weekly</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Once every two weeks</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Once monthly</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>Less frequently than once monthly</td></tr> </table>	1	Several times daily	2	Once daily	3	2 - 3 times weekly	4	Once weekly	5	Once every two weeks	6	Once monthly	7	Less frequently than once monthly
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3	2 - 3 times weekly															
4	Once weekly															
5	Once every two weeks															
6	Once monthly															
7	Less frequently than once monthly															
generated_note_name_419	Dog	User entered text														
an0houdogoft	How often does this occur?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Several times daily</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Once daily</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>2 - 3 times weekly</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Once weekly</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Once every two weeks</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Once monthly</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>Less frequently than once monthly</td></tr> </table>	1	Several times daily	2	Once daily	3	2 - 3 times weekly	4	Once weekly	5	Once every two weeks	6	Once monthly	7	Less frequently than once monthly
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4	Once weekly															
5	Once every two weeks															
6	Once monthly															
7	Less frequently than once monthly															
generated_note_name_421	Cat	User entered text														
an0houcatoft	How often does this occur?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Several times daily</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Once daily</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>2 - 3 times weekly</td></tr> </table>	1	Several times daily	2	Once daily	3	2 - 3 times weekly								
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4	Once weekly															
5	Once every two weeks															
6	Once monthly															
7	Less frequently than once monthly															
generated_note_name_423	Horse	User entered text														
an0houhoroft	How often does this occur?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Several times daily</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Once daily</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>2 - 3 times weekly</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Once weekly</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Once every two weeks</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Once monthly</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>Less frequently than once monthly</td></tr> </table>	1	Several times daily	2	Once daily	3	2 - 3 times weekly	4	Once weekly	5	Once every two weeks	6	Once monthly	7	Less frequently than once monthly
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4	Once weekly															
5	Once every two weeks															
6	Once monthly															
7	Less frequently than once monthly															
generated_note_name_425	Donkey	User entered text														
an0houdonoft	How often does this occur?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Several times daily</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Once daily</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>2 - 3 times weekly</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Once weekly</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Once every two weeks</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Once monthly</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>Less frequently than once monthly</td></tr> </table>	1	Several times daily	2	Once daily	3	2 - 3 times weekly	4	Once weekly	5	Once every two weeks	6	Once monthly	7	Less frequently than once monthly
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4	Once weekly															
5	Once every two weeks															
6	Once monthly															
7	Less frequently than once monthly															
generated_note_name_427	Chicken	User entered text														
an0houchioft	How often does this occur?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Several times daily</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Once daily</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>2 - 3 times weekly</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Once weekly</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Once every two weeks</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Once monthly</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>Less frequently than once monthly</td></tr> </table>	1	Several times daily	2	Once daily	3	2 - 3 times weekly	4	Once weekly	5	Once every two weeks	6	Once monthly	7	Less frequently than once monthly
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5	Once every two weeks															
6	Once monthly															
7	Less frequently than once monthly															

generated_note_name_429	#{6}	User entered text														
an0houothoft	How often does this occur?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Several times daily</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Once daily</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>2 - 3 times weekly</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Once weekly</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Once every two weeks</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Once monthly</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>Less frequently than once monthly</td></tr> </table>	1	Several times daily	2	Once daily	3	2 - 3 times weekly	4	Once weekly	5	Once every two weeks	6	Once monthly	7	Less frequently than once monthly
1	Several times daily															
2	Once daily															
3	2 - 3 times weekly															
4	Once weekly															
5	Once every two weeks															
6	Once monthly															
7	Less frequently than once monthly															
grpHowAnimalsContained	Hidden from user															
generated_note_name_433	If any animals are kept in the house, how are they contained?	User entered text														
hou0ovcow	Cow	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Free roaming</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Restricted to one room</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Custom made pen</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Chained up</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Free roaming	2	Restricted to one room	3	Custom made pen	4	Chained up	5	Other				
1	Free roaming															
2	Restricted to one room															
3	Custom made pen															
4	Chained up															
5	Other															
hou0ovpig	Pig	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Free roaming</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Restricted to one room</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Custom made pen</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Chained up</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Free roaming	2	Restricted to one room	3	Custom made pen	4	Chained up	5	Other				
1	Free roaming															
2	Restricted to one room															
3	Custom made pen															
4	Chained up															
5	Other															
hou0ovshe	Sheep	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Free roaming</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Restricted to one room</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Custom made pen</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Chained up</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Free roaming	2	Restricted to one room	3	Custom made pen	4	Chained up	5	Other				
1	Free roaming															
2	Restricted to one room															
3	Custom made pen															
4	Chained up															
5	Other															
hou0ovgoa	Goat	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Free roaming</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Restricted to one room</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Custom made pen</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Chained up</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Free roaming	2	Restricted to one room	3	Custom made pen	4	Chained up	5	Other				
1	Free roaming															
2	Restricted to one room															
3	Custom made pen															
4	Chained up															
5	Other															

hou0ovdog	Dog	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Free roaming</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Restricted to one room</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Custom made pen</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Chained up</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Free roaming	2	Restricted to one room	3	Custom made pen	4	Chained up	5	Other
1	Free roaming											
2	Restricted to one room											
3	Custom made pen											
4	Chained up											
5	Other											
hou0ovcat	Cat	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Free roaming</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Restricted to one room</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Custom made pen</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Chained up</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Free roaming	2	Restricted to one room	3	Custom made pen	4	Chained up	5	Other
1	Free roaming											
2	Restricted to one room											
3	Custom made pen											
4	Chained up											
5	Other											
hou0ovhor	Horse	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Free roaming</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Restricted to one room</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Custom made pen</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Chained up</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Free roaming	2	Restricted to one room	3	Custom made pen	4	Chained up	5	Other
1	Free roaming											
2	Restricted to one room											
3	Custom made pen											
4	Chained up											
5	Other											
hou0ovdon	Donkey	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Free roaming</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Restricted to one room</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Custom made pen</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Chained up</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Free roaming	2	Restricted to one room	3	Custom made pen	4	Chained up	5	Other
1	Free roaming											
2	Restricted to one room											
3	Custom made pen											
4	Chained up											
5	Other											
hou0ovir	Chicken	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Free roaming</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Restricted to one room</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Custom made pen</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Chained up</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Free roaming	2	Restricted to one room	3	Custom made pen	4	Chained up	5	Other
1	Free roaming											
2	Restricted to one room											
3	Custom made pen											
4	Chained up											
5	Other											
hou0ovoth1	\${3}	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Free roaming</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Restricted to one room</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Custom made pen</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Chained up</td></tr> </table>	1	Free roaming	2	Restricted to one room	3	Custom made pen	4	Chained up		
1	Free roaming											
2	Restricted to one room											
3	Custom made pen											
4	Chained up											

		5 Other										
hou0ovoth2	#{4}	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Free roaming</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Restricted to one room</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Custom made pen</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Chained up</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Free roaming	2	Restricted to one room	3	Custom made pen	4	Chained up	5	Other
1	Free roaming											
2	Restricted to one room											
3	Custom made pen											
4	Chained up											
5	Other											
hou0ovoth3	#{5}	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Free roaming</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Restricted to one room</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Custom made pen</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Chained up</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Free roaming	2	Restricted to one room	3	Custom made pen	4	Chained up	5	Other
1	Free roaming											
2	Restricted to one room											
3	Custom made pen											
4	Chained up											
5	Other											
grpLivingArrangement	Hidden from user											
generated_note_name_448	What are the living arrangements of humans and animals?	User entered text										
liv0cow	Cow	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Cattle in the same room as humans overnight</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Cattle in the same house but not same room as humans overnight</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>No cattle in the house overnight</td></tr> </table>	1	Cattle in the same room as humans overnight	2	Cattle in the same house but not same room as humans overnight	3	No cattle in the house overnight				
1	Cattle in the same room as humans overnight											
2	Cattle in the same house but not same room as humans overnight											
3	No cattle in the house overnight											
liv0pig	Pig	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Pig in the same room as humans overnight</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Pig in the same house but not same room as humans overnight</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>No Pig in the house overnight</td></tr> </table>	1	Pig in the same room as humans overnight	2	Pig in the same house but not same room as humans overnight	3	No Pig in the house overnight				
1	Pig in the same room as humans overnight											
2	Pig in the same house but not same room as humans overnight											
3	No Pig in the house overnight											
liv0she	Sheep	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Sheep in the same room as humans overnight</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Sheep in the same house but not same room as humans</td></tr> </table>	1	Sheep in the same room as humans overnight	2	Sheep in the same house but not same room as humans						
1	Sheep in the same room as humans overnight											
2	Sheep in the same house but not same room as humans											

		<table border="1"> <tr> <td></td> <td>overnight</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>No Sheep in the house overnight</td> </tr> </table>		overnight	3	No Sheep in the house overnight		
	overnight							
3	No Sheep in the house overnight							
liv0goa	Goat	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Goat in the same room as humans overnight</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Goat in the same house but not same room as humans overnight</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>No Goat in the house overnight</td> </tr> </table>	1	Goat in the same room as humans overnight	2	Goat in the same house but not same room as humans overnight	3	No Goat in the house overnight
1	Goat in the same room as humans overnight							
2	Goat in the same house but not same room as humans overnight							
3	No Goat in the house overnight							
liv0dog	Dog	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Dog in the same room as humans overnight</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Dog in the same house but not same room as humans overnight</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>No Dog in the house overnight</td> </tr> </table>	1	Dog in the same room as humans overnight	2	Dog in the same house but not same room as humans overnight	3	No Dog in the house overnight
1	Dog in the same room as humans overnight							
2	Dog in the same house but not same room as humans overnight							
3	No Dog in the house overnight							
liv0cat	Cat	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Cat in the same room as humans overnight</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Cat in the same house but not same room as humans overnight</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>No Cat in the house overnight</td> </tr> </table>	1	Cat in the same room as humans overnight	2	Cat in the same house but not same room as humans overnight	3	No Cat in the house overnight
1	Cat in the same room as humans overnight							
2	Cat in the same house but not same room as humans overnight							
3	No Cat in the house overnight							
liv0hor	Horse	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Horse in the same room as humans overnight</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Horse in the same house but not same room as humans overnight</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>No Horse in the house overnight</td> </tr> </table>	1	Horse in the same room as humans overnight	2	Horse in the same house but not same room as humans overnight	3	No Horse in the house overnight
1	Horse in the same room as humans overnight							
2	Horse in the same house but not same room as humans overnight							
3	No Horse in the house overnight							
liv0don	Donkey	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Donkey in the same room as humans overnight</td> </tr> </table>	1	Donkey in the same room as humans overnight				
1	Donkey in the same room as humans overnight							

		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Donkey in the same house but not same room as humans overnight</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>No Donkey in the house overnight</td> </tr> </table>	2	Donkey in the same house but not same room as humans overnight	3	No Donkey in the house overnight		
2	Donkey in the same house but not same room as humans overnight							
3	No Donkey in the house overnight							
liv0bir	Chicken	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Bird in the same room as humans overnight</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Bird in the same house but not same room as humans overnight</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>No Bird in the house overnight</td> </tr> </table>	1	Bird in the same room as humans overnight	2	Bird in the same house but not same room as humans overnight	3	No Bird in the house overnight
1	Bird in the same room as humans overnight							
2	Bird in the same house but not same room as humans overnight							
3	No Bird in the house overnight							
liv0oth1	#{3}	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Other in the same room as humans overnight</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Other in the same house but not same room as humans overnight</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>No Other in the house overnight</td> </tr> </table>	1	Other in the same room as humans overnight	2	Other in the same house but not same room as humans overnight	3	No Other in the house overnight
1	Other in the same room as humans overnight							
2	Other in the same house but not same room as humans overnight							
3	No Other in the house overnight							
liv0oth2	#{4}	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Other in the same room as humans overnight</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Other in the same house but not same room as humans overnight</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>No Other in the house overnight</td> </tr> </table>	1	Other in the same room as humans overnight	2	Other in the same house but not same room as humans overnight	3	No Other in the house overnight
1	Other in the same room as humans overnight							
2	Other in the same house but not same room as humans overnight							
3	No Other in the house overnight							
liv0oth3	#{5}	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Other in the same room as humans overnight</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Other in the same house but not same room as humans overnight</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>No Other in the house overnight</td> </tr> </table>	1	Other in the same room as humans overnight	2	Other in the same house but not same room as humans overnight	3	No Other in the house overnight
1	Other in the same room as humans overnight							
2	Other in the same house but not same room as humans overnight							
3	No Other in the house overnight							

nonhouan0	Do any non-household members look after the animals?	1	Yes
		0	No
grpLook4Species	Hidden from user		
generated_note_name_464	Which species do they look after?	User entered text	
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_465		1	Yes
		0	No
look4cow	Cow	1	Yes
		0	No
look4pig	Pig	1	Yes
		0	No
look4she	Sheep	1	Yes
		0	No
look4goa	Goat	1	Yes
		0	No
look4dog	Dog	1	Yes
		0	No
look4cat	Cat	1	Yes
		0	No
look4hor	Horse	1	Yes
		0	No
look4don	Donkey	1	Yes
		0	No
look4bird	Bird	1	Yes
		0	No

look4othr1	#{3}	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
look4othr2	#{4}	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
look4othr3	#{5}	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
nw	Hidden from user					
generated_table_list_label_478	Who are these people	User entered text				
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_479		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
nonhouwho1	Relative	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
nonhouwho2	Friend	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
nonhouwho3	Trader	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
nonhouwho4	Other business arrangement	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
nonhouwho9	Other	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
nonhouwho9t	Please specify other	User entered text				
bouan	Have you bought or acquired any animals over the last 6 months?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
bouannum	Hidden from user					

generated_note_name_488	Which species have you bought or acquired?	User entered text	
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_489		1	Yes
		0	No
bouancow	Cow	1	Yes
		0	No
bouanpig	Pig	1	Yes
		0	No
bouanshe	Sheep	1	Yes
		0	No
bouangoa	Goat	1	Yes
		0	No
bouandog	Dog	1	Yes
		0	No
bouancat	Cat	1	Yes
		0	No
bouanhor	Horse	1	Yes
		0	No
bouandon	Donkey	1	Yes
		0	No
bouanchi	Chicken	1	Yes
		0	No
bouanoth1	Other	1	Yes
		0	No

aqothert	Please specify other species acquired	User entered text								
acq	Hidden from user									
bouanwhecow	Where did you acquire the cow(s) from?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Market</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Friend</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Relative</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	Market	2	Friend	3	Relative	4	Other
1	Market									
2	Friend									
3	Relative									
4	Other									
bouannumcow	How many cows have you bought or acquired?	User entered integer								
bouanwhepig	Where did you acquire the pigs from?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Market</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Friend</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Relative</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	Market	2	Friend	3	Relative	4	Other
1	Market									
2	Friend									
3	Relative									
4	Other									
bouannumpig	How many pigs have you bought or acquired?	User entered integer								
bouanwheshe	Where did you acquire the sheep from?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Market</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Friend</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Relative</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	Market	2	Friend	3	Relative	4	Other
1	Market									
2	Friend									
3	Relative									
4	Other									
bouannumshe	How many sheep have you bought or acquired?	User entered integer								
bouanwhegoa	Where did you acquire the goats from?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Market</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Friend</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Relative</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	Market	2	Friend	3	Relative	4	Other
1	Market									
2	Friend									
3	Relative									
4	Other									
bouannumgoa	How many goats have you bought or acquired?	User entered integer								
bouanwhedog	Where did you acquire the dogs from?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Market</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Friend</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Relative</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	Market	2	Friend	3	Relative	4	Other
1	Market									
2	Friend									
3	Relative									
4	Other									
bouannumdog	How many dogs have you bought or acquired?	User entered integer								
bouanwhecat	Where did you acquire the cats from?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Market</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Friend</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Relative</td> </tr> </table>	1	Market	2	Friend	3	Relative		
1	Market									
2	Friend									
3	Relative									

		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	4	Other						
4	Other									
bouannumcat	How many cats have you bought or acquired?	User entered integer								
bouanwhehor	Where did you acquire the horses from?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Market</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Friend</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Relative</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	Market	2	Friend	3	Relative	4	Other
1	Market									
2	Friend									
3	Relative									
4	Other									
bouannumhor	How many horses have you bought or acquired?	User entered integer								
bouanwhedon	Where did you acquire the donkeys from?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Market</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Friend</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Relative</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	Market	2	Friend	3	Relative	4	Other
1	Market									
2	Friend									
3	Relative									
4	Other									
bouannumdon	How many donkeys have you bought or acquired?	User entered integer								
bouanwhechi	Where did you acquire the chickens from?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Market</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Friend</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Relative</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	Market	2	Friend	3	Relative	4	Other
1	Market									
2	Friend									
3	Relative									
4	Other									
bouannumchi	How many chickens have you bought or acquired?	User entered integer								
bouanwheoth1	Where did you acquire \${7} from?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Market</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Friend</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Relative</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	Market	2	Friend	3	Relative	4	Other
1	Market									
2	Friend									
3	Relative									
4	Other									
bouannumoth1	How many of \${7} have you bought or acquired?	User entered integer								
grpWasteConsumption	Hidden from user									
anea0toi	Do any animals regularly consume waste from the human toilet?	User entered text								
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_525		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No				
1	Yes									
0	No									
anea0toicow	Cow	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No				
1	Yes									
0	No									

anea0toipig	Pig	1	Yes
		0	No
anea0toishe	Sheep	1	Yes
		0	No
anea0toigoa	Goat	1	Yes
		0	No
anea0toidog	Dog	1	Yes
		0	No
anea0toicat	Cat	1	Yes
		0	No
anea0toihor	Horse	1	Yes
		0	No
anea0toidon	Donkey	1	Yes
		0	No
anea0toichi	Chicken	1	Yes
		0	No
anea1toioth	3	1	Yes
		0	No
anea2toioth	4	1	Yes
		0	No
anea3toioth	5	1	Yes
		0	No
solan	Have you sold any animals over the last 6 months?	1	Yes

		0	No
sol	Hidden from user		
generated_note_name_540	Which species have you sold?	User entered text	
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_541		1	Yes
		0	No
solancow	Cow	1	Yes
		0	No
solanpig	Pig	1	Yes
		0	No
solanshe	Sheep	1	Yes
		0	No
solangoa	Goat	1	Yes
		0	No
solandog	Dog	1	Yes
		0	No
solancat	Cat	1	Yes
		0	No
solanhor	Horse	1	Yes
		0	No
solandon	Donkey	1	Yes
		0	No
solanchi	Chicken	1	Yes
		0	No
solanoth1	Other		

		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No								
1	Yes													
0	No													
solanoth1sp	Please specify other species that you have sold	User entered text												
soland	Hidden from user													
generated_note_name_555	Cows	User entered text												
solancowwho	To whom did you sell a cow?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Direct to friend</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Market</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Trader</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Slaughterhouse</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Relative</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	Direct to friend	2	Market	3	Trader	4	Slaughterhouse	5	Relative	6	Other
1	Direct to friend													
2	Market													
3	Trader													
4	Slaughterhouse													
5	Relative													
6	Other													
solancowdist	When you sell a cow, how far away from where you keep it does it normally travel?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>0-5miles</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>5-10miles</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>10-15miles</td> </tr> </table>	1	0-5miles	2	5-10miles	3	10-15miles						
1	0-5miles													
2	5-10miles													
3	10-15miles													
generated_note_name_558	Pigs	User entered text												
solanpigwho	To whom did you sell a pig to?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Direct to friend</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Market</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Trader</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Slaughterhouse</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Relative</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	Direct to friend	2	Market	3	Trader	4	Slaughterhouse	5	Relative	6	Other
1	Direct to friend													
2	Market													
3	Trader													
4	Slaughterhouse													
5	Relative													
6	Other													
solanpigdist	When you sell a pig, how far away from where you keep it does it normally travel?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>0-5miles</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>5-10miles</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>10-15miles</td> </tr> </table>	1	0-5miles	2	5-10miles	3	10-15miles						
1	0-5miles													
2	5-10miles													
3	10-15miles													
generated_note_name_561	Sheep	User entered text												
solanshewho	To whom did you sell a sheep to?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Direct to friend</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Market</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Trader</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Slaughterhouse</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Relative</td> </tr> </table>	1	Direct to friend	2	Market	3	Trader	4	Slaughterhouse	5	Relative		
1	Direct to friend													
2	Market													
3	Trader													
4	Slaughterhouse													
5	Relative													

		6 Other												
solanshedist	When you sell a sheep, how far away from where you keep it does it normally travel?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>0-5miles</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>5-10miles</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>10-15miles</td> </tr> </table>	1	0-5miles	2	5-10miles	3	10-15miles						
1	0-5miles													
2	5-10miles													
3	10-15miles													
generated_note_name_564	Goats	User entered text												
solangoawho	To whom did you sell a goat to?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Direct to friend</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Market</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Trader</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Slaughterhouse</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Relative</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	Direct to friend	2	Market	3	Trader	4	Slaughterhouse	5	Relative	6	Other
1	Direct to friend													
2	Market													
3	Trader													
4	Slaughterhouse													
5	Relative													
6	Other													
solangoadist	When you sell a goat, how far away from where you keep it does it normally travel?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>0-5miles</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>5-10miles</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>10-15miles</td> </tr> </table>	1	0-5miles	2	5-10miles	3	10-15miles						
1	0-5miles													
2	5-10miles													
3	10-15miles													
generated_note_name_567	Dogs	User entered text												
solandogwho	To whom did you sell a dog to?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Direct to friend</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Market</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Trader</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Slaughterhouse</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Relative</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	Direct to friend	2	Market	3	Trader	4	Slaughterhouse	5	Relative	6	Other
1	Direct to friend													
2	Market													
3	Trader													
4	Slaughterhouse													
5	Relative													
6	Other													
solandogdist	When you sell a dog, how far away from where you keep it does it normally travel?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>0-5miles</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>5-10miles</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>10-15miles</td> </tr> </table>	1	0-5miles	2	5-10miles	3	10-15miles						
1	0-5miles													
2	5-10miles													
3	10-15miles													
solancatwho	Where did you sell these animals to?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Direct to friend</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Market</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Trader</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Slaughterhouse</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Relative</td> </tr> </table>	1	Direct to friend	2	Market	3	Trader	4	Slaughterhouse	5	Relative		
1	Direct to friend													
2	Market													
3	Trader													
4	Slaughterhouse													
5	Relative													

		6 Other												
generated_note_name_571	Cat	User entered text												
solancatdist	When you sell a cat, how far away from where you keep it does it normally travel?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>0-5miles</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>5-10miles</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>10-15miles</td> </tr> </table>	1	0-5miles	2	5-10miles	3	10-15miles						
1	0-5miles													
2	5-10miles													
3	10-15miles													
solanhorwho	To whom did you sell these animals to?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Direct to friend</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Market</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Trader</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Slaughterhouse</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Relative</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	Direct to friend	2	Market	3	Trader	4	Slaughterhouse	5	Relative	6	Other
1	Direct to friend													
2	Market													
3	Trader													
4	Slaughterhouse													
5	Relative													
6	Other													
generated_note_name_574	Horse	User entered text												
solanhordist	When you sell a horse, how far away from where you keep it does it normally travel?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>0-5miles</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>5-10miles</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>10-15miles</td> </tr> </table>	1	0-5miles	2	5-10miles	3	10-15miles						
1	0-5miles													
2	5-10miles													
3	10-15miles													
solandonwho	To whom did you sell these animals to?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Direct to friend</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Market</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Trader</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Slaughterhouse</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Relative</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	Direct to friend	2	Market	3	Trader	4	Slaughterhouse	5	Relative	6	Other
1	Direct to friend													
2	Market													
3	Trader													
4	Slaughterhouse													
5	Relative													
6	Other													
generated_note_name_577	Donkey	User entered text												
solandondist	When you sell a donkey, how far away from where you keep it does it normally travel?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>0-5miles</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>5-10miles</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>10-15miles</td> </tr> </table>	1	0-5miles	2	5-10miles	3	10-15miles						
1	0-5miles													
2	5-10miles													
3	10-15miles													
solanchiwho	To whom did you sell these animals to?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Direct to friend</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Market</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Trader</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Slaughterhouse</td> </tr> </table>	1	Direct to friend	2	Market	3	Trader	4	Slaughterhouse				
1	Direct to friend													
2	Market													
3	Trader													
4	Slaughterhouse													

		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Relative</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	5	Relative	6	Other								
5	Relative													
6	Other													
generated_note_name_580	Chicken	User entered text												
solanchidist	When you sell a chicken how far away from where you keep it does it normally travel?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>0-5miles</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>5-10miles</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>10-15miles</td> </tr> </table>	1	0-5miles	2	5-10miles	3	10-15miles						
1	0-5miles													
2	5-10miles													
3	10-15miles													
solanoth1who	To whom did you sell \${8} to?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Direct to friend</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Market</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Trader</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Slaughterhouse</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Relative</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	Direct to friend	2	Market	3	Trader	4	Slaughterhouse	5	Relative	6	Other
1	Direct to friend													
2	Market													
3	Trader													
4	Slaughterhouse													
5	Relative													
6	Other													
solanoth1dist	When you sell an animal, how far away from where you keep it does it normally travel?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>0-5miles</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>5-10miles</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>10-15miles</td> </tr> </table>	1	0-5miles	2	5-10miles	3	10-15miles						
1	0-5miles													
2	5-10miles													
3	10-15miles													
prot	Is any protective clothing worn when you handle animals?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No								
1	Yes													
0	No													
pcl	Hidden from user													
protwhispp	Which species are you dealing with when protective clothing is worn?	User entered text												
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_588		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No								
1	Yes													
0	No													
protcow	Cow	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No								
1	Yes													
0	No													
protpig	Pig	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No								
1	Yes													
0	No													
protshe	Sheep	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes										
1	Yes													

		0	No
protgoa	Goat	1	Yes
		0	No
protdog	Dog	1	Yes
		0	No
protcat	Cat	1	Yes
		0	No
prothor	Horse	1	Yes
		0	No
protdon	Donkey	1	Yes
		0	No
protchi	Chicken	1	Yes
		0	No
proth1	#{3}	1	Yes
		0	No
proth2	#{4}	1	Yes
		0	No
proth3	#{5}	1	Yes
		0	No
pcc	Hidden from user		
pcc1	Hidden from user		
generated_table_list_label_602	What protective clothing is worn when handling cows?	User entered text	
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_603		1	Yes
		0	No

protcowwhat1	Gloves	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
protcowwhat2	Coat	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
protcowwhat3	Boots	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
protcowwhat4	Hat	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
protcowwhat9	Other	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
protcowwhat9t	Please specify other type of protective clothing worn	User entered text				
pcc2	Hidden from user					
generated_table_list_label_610	When is protective clothing worn when handling cows	User entered text				
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_611		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
protcowwhen1	During help giving birth	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
protcowwhen2	When cleaning out pens	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
protcowwhen3	Moving animals around	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
protcowwhen4	Feeding animals	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
protcowwhen9	Other	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes		
1	Yes					

		0	No
protcowwhen9t	Please specify when protective clothing is worn	User entered text	
pcp	Hidden from user		
pcp1	Hidden from user		
generated_table_list_label_620	What protective clothing is worn when handling Pigs?	User entered text	
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_621		1	Yes
		0	No
protpigwhat1	Gloves	1	Yes
		0	No
protpigwhat2	Coat	1	Yes
		0	No
protpigwhat3	Boots	1	Yes
		0	No
protpigwhat4	Hat	1	Yes
		0	No
protpigwhat9	Other	1	Yes
		0	No
protpigwhat9t	Please specify other type of protective clothing worn	User entered text	
pcp2	Hidden from user		
generated_table_list_label_628	When is protective clothing worn when handling Pigs	User entered text	
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_629		1	Yes
		0	No
protpigwhen1	During help giving birth	1	Yes
		0	No
protpigwhen2	When cleaning out pens	1	Yes
		0	No

protpigwhen3	Moving animals around	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
protpigwhen4	Feeding animals	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
protpigwhen9	Other	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
protpigwhen9t	Please specify when protective clothing is worn	User entered text				
pcs	Hidden from user					
pcs1	Hidden from user					
generated_table_list_label_638	What protective clothing is worn when handling Sheep?	User entered text				
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_639		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
protshewhat1	Gloves	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
protshewhat2	Coat	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
protshewhat3	Boots	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
protshewhat4	Hat	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
protshewhat9	Other	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
protshewhat9t	Please specify other type of protective clothing worn	User entered text				
pcs2	Hidden from user					

generated_table_list_label_646	When is protective clothing worn when handling Sheep	User entered text				
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_647		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
protshewhen1	During help giving birth	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
protshewhen2	When cleaning out pens	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
protshewhen3	Moving animals around	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
protshewhen4	Feeding animals	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
protshewhen9	Other	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
protshewhen9t	Please specify when protective clothing is worn	User entered text				
pcg	Hidden from user					
pcg1	Hidden from user					
generated_table_list_label_656	What protective clothing is worn when handling Goats?	User entered text				
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_657		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
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0	No					
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1	Yes					
0	No					
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1	Yes					
0	No					
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1	Yes					
0	No					

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0	No					
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0	No					
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pcg2	Hidden from user					
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0	No					
protgoawhen1	During help giving birth	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
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0	No					
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0	No					
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0	No					
protgoawhen4	Feeding animals	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
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0	No					
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0	No					
protgoawhen9t	Please specify when protective clothing is worn	User entered text				
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pcd1	Hidden from user					
generated_table_list_label_674	What protective clothing is worn when handling Dogs?	User entered text				
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0	No					
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0	No					
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1	Yes					
0	No					
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0	No					
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0	No					
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0	No					
protdogwhat9t	Please specify other type of protective clothing worn	User entered text				
pcd2	Hidden from user					
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0	No					
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1	Yes					
0	No					
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1	Yes					
0	No					
protdogwhen3	Moving animals around	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
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0	No					
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1	Yes					
0	No					

protdogwhen9t	Please specify when protective clothing is worn	User entered text				
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pccc1	Hidden from user					
generated_table_list_label_692	What protective clothing is worn when handling Cats?	User entered text				
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0	No					
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0	No					
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1	Yes					
0	No					
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0	No					
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0	No					
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0	No					
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pccc2	Hidden from user					
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0	No					
protcatwhen1	During help giving birth	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
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1	Yes					
0	No					

protcatwhen3	Moving animals around	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
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0	No					
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0	No					
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0	No					
protcatwhen9t	Please specify when protective clothing is worn	User entered text				
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pch1	Hidden from user					
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0	No					
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0	No					
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1	Yes					
0	No					
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0	No					
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0	No					
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1	Yes					
0	No					
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0	No					
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0	No					
prothorwhen4	Feeding animals	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
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0	No					
prothorwhen9t	Please specify when protective clothing is worn	User entered text				
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pcdon1	Hidden from user					
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0	No					
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1	Yes					

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0	No					
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0	No					
protndonwhen3	Moving animals around	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
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0	No					
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pcch1	Hidden from user					
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1	Yes					

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		0	No
protchiwhat3	Boots	1	Yes
		0	No
protchiwhat4	Hat	1	Yes
		0	No
protchiwhat9	Other	1	Yes
		0	No
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pch2	Hidden from user		
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protchiwhen2	When cleaning out pens	1	Yes
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protchiwhen3	Moving animals around	1	Yes
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protchiwhen4	Feeding animals	1	Yes
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protchiwhen9	Other	1	Yes
		0	No

protchiwhen9t	Please specify when protective clothing is worn	User entered text				
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pcosp1	Hidden from user					
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0	No					
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0	No					
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0	No					
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0	No					
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0	No					
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0	No					
protosp1when1	During help giving birth	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
protosp1when2	When cleaning out pens	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
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protosp1when3	Moving animals around	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
protosp1when4	Feeding animals	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
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0	No					
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0	No					
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0	No					
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1	Yes					
0	No					
protosp2what3	Boots	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
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protosp2what4	Hat	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
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0	No					
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0	No					
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1	Yes					
0	No					
protosp2when2	When cleaning out pens	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
protosp2when3	Moving animals around	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
protosp2when4	Feeding animals	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
protosp2when9	Other	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
protosp2when9t	Please specify when protective clothing is worn	User entered text				
gpcosp3	Hidden from user					
pcosp3	Hidden from user					
generated_table_list_label_800	What protective clothing is worn when handling \${5}?	User entered text				
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_801		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
protosp3what1	Gloves	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
protosp3what2	Coat	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
protosp3what3	Boots	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
protosp3what4	Hat	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes		
1	Yes					

		0	No
protosp3what9	Other	1	Yes
		0	No
protosp3what9t	Please specify other type of protective clothing worn	User entered text	
pcosp3g	Hidden from user		
generated_table_list_label_808	When is protective clothing worn when handling \${5}	User entered text	
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_809		1	Yes
		0	No
protosp3when1	During help giving birth	1	Yes
		0	No
protosp3when2	When cleaning out pens	1	Yes
		0	No
protosp3when3	Moving animals around	1	Yes
		0	No
protosp3when4	Feeding animals	1	Yes
		0	No
protosp3when9	Other	1	Yes
		0	No
protosp3when9t	Please specify when protective clothing is worn	User entered text	
urfaediff	Is urine from animals disposed of differently from animal faecal material (manure)?	1	Yes
		0	No
howur	How is animal urine disposed of?	1	Deposited outside the household perimete
		2	Deposited inside the household perimeter
		3	Left where the animal passes

		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Used for fertiliser on own crops</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Sold/given for fertiliser on others' crops</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>Moved to a certain area</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	4	Used for fertiliser on own crops	5	Sold/given for fertiliser on others' crops	6	Moved to a certain area	7	Other						
4	Used for fertiliser on own crops															
5	Sold/given for fertiliser on others' crops															
6	Moved to a certain area															
7	Other															
howuroth	Specify other way urine is disposed of	User entered text														
howfaedis	How is animal faecal material disposed of?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Deposited outside the household perimete</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Deposited inside the household perimeter</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Left where the animal passes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Used for fertiliser on own crops</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Sold/given for fertiliser on others' crops</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>Moved to a certain area</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	Deposited outside the household perimete	2	Deposited inside the household perimeter	3	Left where the animal passes	4	Used for fertiliser on own crops	5	Sold/given for fertiliser on others' crops	6	Moved to a certain area	7	Other
1	Deposited outside the household perimete															
2	Deposited inside the household perimeter															
3	Left where the animal passes															
4	Used for fertiliser on own crops															
5	Sold/given for fertiliser on others' crops															
6	Moved to a certain area															
7	Other															
movwhere	Where is this certain area?	User entered text														
howfaedisoth	Specify other way faecal is disposed of	User entered text														
mbreedaw	Do you own any male animals which are taken to another premises for breeding?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No										
1	Yes															
0	No															
manin	Hidden from user															
mbreedawwhi	If yes, which ones	User entered text														
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_826		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No										
1	Yes															
0	No															
mbreedbull	Bull	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No										
1	Yes															
0	No															
mbredram	Ram	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No										
1	Yes															
0	No															

mbreedbilly	Billy goat	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No				
1	Yes									
0	No									
mbreedcock	Cockeral	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No				
1	Yes									
0	No									
mbreedaw1	\${3}	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No				
1	Yes									
0	No									
mbreedaw2	\${4}	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No				
1	Yes									
0	No									
mbreedaw3	\${5}	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No				
1	Yes									
0	No									
maanild	Hidden from user									
generated_note_name_835	Bulls	User entered text								
mbreedbulloft	How often are they used for breeding?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Weekly</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Monthly</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Every 6 months</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Annually</td> </tr> </table>	1	Weekly	2	Monthly	3	Every 6 months	4	Annually
1	Weekly									
2	Monthly									
3	Every 6 months									
4	Annually									
mbreedbullar	How far do they travel to breed?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>0-5miles</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>5-10miles</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>10-15miles</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Further</td> </tr> </table>	1	0-5miles	2	5-10miles	3	10-15miles	4	Further
1	0-5miles									
2	5-10miles									
3	10-15miles									
4	Further									
generated_note_name_838	Ram	User entered text								
mbreedramoft	How often are they used for breeding?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Weekly</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Monthly</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Every 6 months</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Annually</td> </tr> </table>	1	Weekly	2	Monthly	3	Every 6 months	4	Annually
1	Weekly									
2	Monthly									
3	Every 6 months									
4	Annually									
mbreedramfar	How far do they travel to breed?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>0-5miles</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>5-10miles</td> </tr> </table>	1	0-5miles	2	5-10miles				
1	0-5miles									
2	5-10miles									

		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>10-15miles</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Further</td> </tr> </table>	3	10-15miles	4	Further				
3	10-15miles									
4	Further									
generated_note_name_841	Billy goat	User entered text								
mbreedbillyoft	How often are they used for breeding?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Weekly</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Monthly</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Every 6 months</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Annually</td> </tr> </table>	1	Weekly	2	Monthly	3	Every 6 months	4	Annually
1	Weekly									
2	Monthly									
3	Every 6 months									
4	Annually									
mbreedbillyar	How far do they travel to breed?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>0-5miles</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>5-10miles</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>10-15miles</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Further</td> </tr> </table>	1	0-5miles	2	5-10miles	3	10-15miles	4	Further
1	0-5miles									
2	5-10miles									
3	10-15miles									
4	Further									
generated_note_name_844	Cockeral	User entered text								
mbreedcockoft	How often are they used for breeding?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Weekly</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Monthly</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Every 6 months</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Annually</td> </tr> </table>	1	Weekly	2	Monthly	3	Every 6 months	4	Annually
1	Weekly									
2	Monthly									
3	Every 6 months									
4	Annually									
mbreedcockfar	How far do they travel to breed?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>0-5miles</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>5-10miles</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>10-15miles</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Further</td> </tr> </table>	1	0-5miles	2	5-10miles	3	10-15miles	4	Further
1	0-5miles									
2	5-10miles									
3	10-15miles									
4	Further									
generated_note_name_847	#{3}	User entered text								
mbreedoth1oft	How often are they used for breeding?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Weekly</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Monthly</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Every 6 months</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Annually</td> </tr> </table>	1	Weekly	2	Monthly	3	Every 6 months	4	Annually
1	Weekly									
2	Monthly									
3	Every 6 months									
4	Annually									
mbreedoth1far	How far do they travel to breed?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>0-5miles</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>5-10miles</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>10-15miles</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	1	0-5miles	2	5-10miles	3	10-15miles		
1	0-5miles									
2	5-10miles									
3	10-15miles									

		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Further</td> </tr> </table>	4	Further						
4	Further									
generated_note_name_850	#{4}	User entered text								
mbreedoft2	How often are they used for breeding?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Weekly</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Monthly</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Every 6 months</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Annually</td> </tr> </table>	1	Weekly	2	Monthly	3	Every 6 months	4	Annually
1	Weekly									
2	Monthly									
3	Every 6 months									
4	Annually									
mbreedfar2	How far do they travel to breed?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>0-5miles</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>5-10miles</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>10-15miles</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Further</td> </tr> </table>	1	0-5miles	2	5-10miles	3	10-15miles	4	Further
1	0-5miles									
2	5-10miles									
3	10-15miles									
4	Further									
generated_note_name_853	#{5}	User entered text								
mbreedoft3	How often are they used for breeding?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Weekly</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Monthly</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Every 6 months</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Annually</td> </tr> </table>	1	Weekly	2	Monthly	3	Every 6 months	4	Annually
1	Weekly									
2	Monthly									
3	Every 6 months									
4	Annually									
mbreedfar3	How far do they travel to breed?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>0-5miles</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>5-10miles</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>10-15miles</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Further</td> </tr> </table>	1	0-5miles	2	5-10miles	3	10-15miles	4	Further
1	0-5miles									
2	5-10miles									
3	10-15miles									
4	Further									
slau	Hidden from user									
wheslau0cow	Cow	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>At home</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>At slaughterhouse</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	At home	2	At slaughterhouse	3	Other		
1	At home									
2	At slaughterhouse									
3	Other									
wheslau0pig	Pig	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>At home</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>At slaughterhouse</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	At home	2	At slaughterhouse	3	Other		
1	At home									
2	At slaughterhouse									
3	Other									
wheslau0she	Sheep	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>At home</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>At slaughterhouse</td> </tr> </table>	1	At home	2	At slaughterhouse				
1	At home									
2	At slaughterhouse									

		3 Other						
wheslau0goa	Goat	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>At home</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>At slaughterhouse</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	At home	2	At slaughterhouse	3	Other
1	At home							
2	At slaughterhouse							
3	Other							
wheslau0chi	Chicken	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>At home</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>At slaughterhouse</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	At home	2	At slaughterhouse	3	Other
1	At home							
2	At slaughterhouse							
3	Other							
wheslau0other1	#{3}	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>At home</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>At slaughterhouse</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	At home	2	At slaughterhouse	3	Other
1	At home							
2	At slaughterhouse							
3	Other							
wheslau0other2	#{4}	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>At home</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>At slaughterhouse</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	At home	2	At slaughterhouse	3	Other
1	At home							
2	At slaughterhouse							
3	Other							
wheslau0other3	#{5}	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>At home</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>At slaughterhouse</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	At home	2	At slaughterhouse	3	Other
1	At home							
2	At slaughterhouse							
3	Other							
slaus	Hidden from user							
owheslau0cow	Please specify where cows are slaughtered.	User entered text						
owheslau0pig	Please specify where pigs are slaughtered.	User entered text						
owheslau0she	Please specify where sheep are slaughtered.	User entered text						
owheslau0goa	Please specify where goats are slaughtered.	User entered text						
owheslau0chi	Please specify where chicken are slaughtered.	User entered text						
owheslau0other1	Please specify where #{3} are slaughtered.	User entered text						
owheslau0other2	Please specify where #{4} are slaughtered.	User entered text						
owheslau0other3	Please specify where #{5} are slaughtered.	User entered text						
wheslauwhecow	Where is the slaughterhouse for cows?	User entered text						
wheslauwhepig	Where is this slaughterhouse for pigs?	User entered text						
wheslauwheshe	Where is this slaughterhouse for sheep?	User entered text						
wheslauwhegoa	Where is this slaughterhouse for goats?	User entered text						

wheslauwhechi	Where is this slaughterhouse for chickens?	User entered text				
wheslauwheoth1	Where is this slaughterhouse for \${3} ?	User entered text				
wheslauwheoth2	Where is this slaughterhouse for \${4} ?	User entered text				
wheslauwheoth3	Where is this slaughterhouse for \${5} ?	User entered text				
marback	Would you ever take animals to the market and bring them back again?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
anmar	Hidden from user					
generated_note_name_887	Which animals?	User entered text				
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_888		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
marbackcow	Cow	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
marbackpig	Pig	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
marbackshe	Sheep	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
marbackgoa	Goat	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
marbackdog	Dog	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
marbackcat	Cat	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
marbackhor	Horse	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
marbackdon	Donkey	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes		
1	Yes					

		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	0	No						
0	No									
marbackchi	Chicken	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No				
1	Yes									
0	No									
marbackoth1	#{3}	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No				
1	Yes									
0	No									
marbackoth2	#{4}	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No				
1	Yes									
0	No									
marbackoth3	#{5}	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No				
1	Yes									
0	No									
anmarg	Hidden from user									
generated_note_name_902	Cow	User entered text								
marbackcowoft	How often does this happen?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Weekly</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Monthly</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Every 6 months</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Annually</td> </tr> </table>	1	Weekly	2	Monthly	3	Every 6 months	4	Annually
1	Weekly									
2	Monthly									
3	Every 6 months									
4	Annually									
generated_note_name_904	Pig	User entered text								
marbackpigoft	How often does this happen?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Weekly</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Monthly</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Every 6 months</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Annually</td> </tr> </table>	1	Weekly	2	Monthly	3	Every 6 months	4	Annually
1	Weekly									
2	Monthly									
3	Every 6 months									
4	Annually									
generated_note_name_906	Sheep	User entered text								
marbacksheoft	How often does this happen?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Weekly</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Monthly</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Every 6 months</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Annually</td> </tr> </table>	1	Weekly	2	Monthly	3	Every 6 months	4	Annually
1	Weekly									
2	Monthly									
3	Every 6 months									
4	Annually									
generated_note_name_908	Goat	User entered text								
marbackgoaft	How often does this happen?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Weekly</td> </tr> </table>	1	Weekly						
1	Weekly									

		<table border="1"> <tr><td>2</td><td>Monthly</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Every 6 months</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Annually</td></tr> </table>	2	Monthly	3	Every 6 months	4	Annually		
2	Monthly									
3	Every 6 months									
4	Annually									
generated_note_name_910	Dog	User entered text								
marbackdogoft	How often does this happen?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Weekly</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Monthly</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Every 6 months</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Annually</td></tr> </table>	1	Weekly	2	Monthly	3	Every 6 months	4	Annually
1	Weekly									
2	Monthly									
3	Every 6 months									
4	Annually									
generated_note_name_912	Cat	User entered text								
marbackcatoft	How often does this happen?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Weekly</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Monthly</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Every 6 months</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Annually</td></tr> </table>	1	Weekly	2	Monthly	3	Every 6 months	4	Annually
1	Weekly									
2	Monthly									
3	Every 6 months									
4	Annually									
generated_note_name_914	Horse	User entered text								
marbackhoroft	How often does this happen?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Weekly</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Monthly</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Every 6 months</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Annually</td></tr> </table>	1	Weekly	2	Monthly	3	Every 6 months	4	Annually
1	Weekly									
2	Monthly									
3	Every 6 months									
4	Annually									
generated_note_name_916	Donkey	User entered text								
marbackdonoft	How often does this happen?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Weekly</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Monthly</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Every 6 months</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Annually</td></tr> </table>	1	Weekly	2	Monthly	3	Every 6 months	4	Annually
1	Weekly									
2	Monthly									
3	Every 6 months									
4	Annually									
generated_note_name_918	Chicken	User entered text								
marbackchioft	If yes, how often does this happen?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Weekly</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Monthly</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Every 6 months</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Annually</td></tr> </table>	1	Weekly	2	Monthly	3	Every 6 months	4	Annually
1	Weekly									
2	Monthly									
3	Every 6 months									
4	Annually									
generated_note_name_920	#{3}	User entered text								

marbackthoft1	If yes, how often does this happen?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Weekly</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Monthly</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Every 6 months</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Annually</td></tr> </table>	1	Weekly	2	Monthly	3	Every 6 months	4	Annually
1	Weekly									
2	Monthly									
3	Every 6 months									
4	Annually									
generated_note_name_922	#{4}	User entered text								
marbackthoft2	If yes, how often does this happen?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Weekly</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Monthly</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Every 6 months</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Annually</td></tr> </table>	1	Weekly	2	Monthly	3	Every 6 months	4	Annually
1	Weekly									
2	Monthly									
3	Every 6 months									
4	Annually									
generated_note_name_924	#{5}	User entered text								
marbackthoft3	If yes, how often does this happen?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Weekly</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Monthly</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Every 6 months</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Annually</td></tr> </table>	1	Weekly	2	Monthly	3	Every 6 months	4	Annually
1	Weekly									
2	Monthly									
3	Every 6 months									
4	Annually									
angi	Have any of your animals developed signs of gastrointestinal illness (diarrhoea, vomiting, weight loss, weakness) over the last six months?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No				
1	Yes									
0	No									
angg	Hidden from user									
generated_note_name_929	If yes which species?	User entered text								
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_930		<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No				
1	Yes									
0	No									
angicow	Cow	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No				
1	Yes									
0	No									
angipig	Pig	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No				
1	Yes									
0	No									
angishe	Sheep	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No				
1	Yes									
0	No									
angigoa	Goat									

		1	Yes
		0	No
angidog	Dog	1	Yes
		0	No
angicat	Cat	1	Yes
		0	No
angihor	Horse	1	Yes
		0	No
angidon	Donkey	1	Yes
		0	No
angichi	Chicken	1	Yes
		0	No
angio1	\${3}	1	Yes
		0	No
angio2	\${4}	1	Yes
		0	No
angio3	\${5}	1	Yes
		0	No
ga	Hidden from user		
angicownum	How many cows have been affected?	User entered integer	
angipignum	How many pigs have been affected?	User entered integer	
angishenum	How many sheep have been affected?	User entered integer	
angigoanum	How many goats have been affected?	User entered integer	
angidognum	How many dogs have been affected?	User entered integer	
angicatnum	How many cats have been affected?	User entered integer	
angihornum	How many horses have been affected?	User entered integer	

angidonnum	How many donkeys have been affected?	User entered integer																		
angichinum	How many chickens have been affected?	User entered integer																		
angiothe1num	How many \${3} have been affected?	User entered integer																		
angiothe2num	How many \${4} have been affected?	User entered integer																		
angiothe3num	How many \${5} have been affected?	User entered integer																		
dis	Hidden from user																			
generated_note_name_958	What do you do in response to disease problems	User entered text																		
dcattle	Cow	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>use traditional medicine</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>use medicine from the veterinary drug store (self-bought)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>consult traditional healer</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>consult assistant veterinary officer</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>consult private veterinarian</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>consult Government veterinarian</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>vet applied/left drugs</td> </tr> <tr> <td>8</td> <td>No sickness</td> </tr> <tr> <td>99</td> <td>other</td> </tr> </table>	1	use traditional medicine	2	use medicine from the veterinary drug store (self-bought)	3	consult traditional healer	4	consult assistant veterinary officer	5	consult private veterinarian	6	consult Government veterinarian	7	vet applied/left drugs	8	No sickness	99	other
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dpig	Pig	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>use traditional medicine</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>use medicine from the veterinary drug store (self-bought)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>consult traditional healer</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>consult assistant veterinary officer</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>consult private veterinarian</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>consult Government veterinarian</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>vet applied/left drugs</td> </tr> <tr> <td>8</td> <td>No sickness</td> </tr> </table>	1	use traditional medicine	2	use medicine from the veterinary drug store (self-bought)	3	consult traditional healer	4	consult assistant veterinary officer	5	consult private veterinarian	6	consult Government veterinarian	7	vet applied/left drugs	8	No sickness		
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		99 other																		
dsheep	Sheep	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>use traditional medicine</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>use medicine from the veterinary drug store (self-bought)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>consult traditional healer</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>consult assistant veterinary officer</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>consult private veterinarian</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>consult Government veterinarian</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>vet applied/left drugs</td> </tr> <tr> <td>8</td> <td>No sickness</td> </tr> <tr> <td>99</td> <td>other</td> </tr> </table>	1	use traditional medicine	2	use medicine from the veterinary drug store (self-bought)	3	consult traditional healer	4	consult assistant veterinary officer	5	consult private veterinarian	6	consult Government veterinarian	7	vet applied/left drugs	8	No sickness	99	other
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dgoat	Goat	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>use traditional medicine</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>use medicine from the veterinary drug store (self-bought)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>consult traditional healer</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>consult assistant veterinary officer</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>consult private veterinarian</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>consult Government veterinarian</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>vet applied/left drugs</td> </tr> <tr> <td>8</td> <td>No sickness</td> </tr> <tr> <td>99</td> <td>other</td> </tr> </table>	1	use traditional medicine	2	use medicine from the veterinary drug store (self-bought)	3	consult traditional healer	4	consult assistant veterinary officer	5	consult private veterinarian	6	consult Government veterinarian	7	vet applied/left drugs	8	No sickness	99	other
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7	vet applied/left drugs																			
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ddog	Dog	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>use traditional medicine</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>use medicine from the veterinary drug store</td> </tr> </table>	1	use traditional medicine	2	use medicine from the veterinary drug store														
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5	consult private veterinarian																			
6	consult Government veterinarian																			
7	vet applied/left drugs																			
8	No sickness																			
99	other																			
dcat	Cat	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>use traditional medicine</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>use medicine from the veterinary drug store (self-bought)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>consult traditional healer</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>consult assistant veterinary officer</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>consult private veterinarian</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>consult Government veterinarian</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>vet applied/left drugs</td> </tr> <tr> <td>8</td> <td>No sickness</td> </tr> <tr> <td>99</td> <td>other</td> </tr> </table>	1	use traditional medicine	2	use medicine from the veterinary drug store (self-bought)	3	consult traditional healer	4	consult assistant veterinary officer	5	consult private veterinarian	6	consult Government veterinarian	7	vet applied/left drugs	8	No sickness	99	other
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dhorse	Horse	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>use traditional medicine</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>use medicine from the veterinary drug store (self-bought)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>consult traditional healer</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>consult assistant veterinary officer</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>consult private</td> </tr> </table>	1	use traditional medicine	2	use medicine from the veterinary drug store (self-bought)	3	consult traditional healer	4	consult assistant veterinary officer	5	consult private								
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			veterinarian
		6	consult Government veterinarian
		7	vet applied/left drugs
		8	No sickness
		99	other
ddonkey	Donkey	1	use traditional medicine
		2	use medicine from the veterinary drug store (self-bought)
		3	consult traditional healer
		4	consult assistant veterinary officer
		5	consult private veterinarian
		6	consult Government veterinarian
		7	vet applied/left drugs
		8	No sickness
		99	other
dpoultry	Chicken	1	use traditional medicine
		2	use medicine from the veterinary drug store (self-bought)
		3	consult traditional healer
		4	consult assistant veterinary officer
		5	consult private veterinarian
		6	consult Government veterinarian
		7	vet applied/left drugs
		8	No sickness
		99	other

doth1	\${3}	<table border="1"> <tr> <td data-bbox="1187 152 1235 253">1</td> <td data-bbox="1235 152 1493 253">use traditional medicine</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1187 253 1235 389">2</td> <td data-bbox="1235 253 1493 389">use medicine from the veterinary drug store (self-bought)</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1187 389 1235 490">3</td> <td data-bbox="1235 389 1493 490">consult traditional healer</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1187 490 1235 591">4</td> <td data-bbox="1235 490 1493 591">consult assistant veterinary officer</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1187 591 1235 692">5</td> <td data-bbox="1235 591 1493 692">consult private veterinarian</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1187 692 1235 792">6</td> <td data-bbox="1235 692 1493 792">consult Government veterinarian</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1187 792 1235 837">7</td> <td data-bbox="1235 792 1493 837">vet applied/left drugs</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1187 837 1235 904">8</td> <td data-bbox="1235 837 1493 904">No sickness</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1187 904 1235 949">99</td> <td data-bbox="1235 904 1493 949">other</td> </tr> </table>	1	use traditional medicine	2	use medicine from the veterinary drug store (self-bought)	3	consult traditional healer	4	consult assistant veterinary officer	5	consult private veterinarian	6	consult Government veterinarian	7	vet applied/left drugs	8	No sickness	99	other
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doth2	\${4}	<table border="1"> <tr> <td data-bbox="1187 1014 1235 1115">1</td> <td data-bbox="1235 1014 1493 1115">use traditional medicine</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1187 1115 1235 1252">2</td> <td data-bbox="1235 1115 1493 1252">use medicine from the veterinary drug store (self-bought)</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1187 1252 1235 1352">3</td> <td data-bbox="1235 1252 1493 1352">consult traditional healer</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1187 1352 1235 1453">4</td> <td data-bbox="1235 1352 1493 1453">consult assistant veterinary officer</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1187 1453 1235 1554">5</td> <td data-bbox="1235 1453 1493 1554">consult private veterinarian</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1187 1554 1235 1655">6</td> <td data-bbox="1235 1554 1493 1655">consult Government veterinarian</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1187 1655 1235 1700">7</td> <td data-bbox="1235 1655 1493 1700">vet applied/left drugs</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1187 1700 1235 1767">8</td> <td data-bbox="1235 1700 1493 1767">No sickness</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1187 1767 1235 1812">99</td> <td data-bbox="1235 1767 1493 1812">other</td> </tr> </table>	1	use traditional medicine	2	use medicine from the veterinary drug store (self-bought)	3	consult traditional healer	4	consult assistant veterinary officer	5	consult private veterinarian	6	consult Government veterinarian	7	vet applied/left drugs	8	No sickness	99	other
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diso	Hidden from user															
odcattle	Please specify what you do in response to Cow diseases	User entered text														
odpig	Please specify what you do in response to Pig diseases	User entered text														
odsheep	Please specify what you do in response to Sheep diseases	User entered text														
odgoat	Please specify what you do in response to Goat diseases	User entered text														
dodog	Please specify what you do in response to Dog diseases	User entered text														
odcat	Please specify what you do in response to Cat diseases	User entered text														
odhorse	Please specify what you do in response to Horse diseases	User entered text														
oddonkey	Please specify what you do in response to Donkey diseases	User entered text														
odpoultry	Please specify what you do in response to Chicken diseases	User entered text														
odoth1	Please specify what you do in response to \${3} diseases	User entered text														
odoth2	Please specify what you do in response to \${4} diseases	User entered text														
odoth3	Please specify what you do in response to \${5} diseases	User entered text														
phc	Do you have access to veterinary services?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No										
1	Yes															
0	No															
accesshc	Which ones do you access to?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Government</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Private full time health worker</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Government and private facilities</td> </tr> </table>	1	Government	2	Private full time health worker	3	Government and private facilities								
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acceslab	Do the animal service include laboratory testing	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No										
1	Yes															
0	No															

uselab	If you have access to lab services do you use it?	1	Yes
		0	No
nuselab	Why don't you use it?	1	not available
		2	not efficient
		3	too expensive
		4	would like more
		5	no need for lab testing
		99	Other
labs	Hidden from user		
generated_note_name_992	Lab services for diagnosis of disease in which species?	User entered text	
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_993		1	Yes
		0	No
lcattle	Cow	1	Yes
		0	No
lpig	Pig	1	Yes
		0	No
lsheep	Sheep	1	Yes
		0	No
lgoat	Goat	1	Yes
		0	No
ldog	Dog	1	Yes
		0	No
lcat	Cat	1	Yes
		0	No
lhorse	Horse	1	Yes
		0	No

ldonkey	Donkey	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
lpoultry	Chicken	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
lother1	\${3}	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
lother2	\${4}	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
lother3	\${5}	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
ahcprog	Is the farm involved in a regular animal health service program, like a vacc campaign etc run by Gov/NGO?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
nameahcprog	If so, what is the name of this?	User entered text				
drg	Hidden from user					
generated_table_list_label_1008	Do you have access to the following	User entered text				
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_1009		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
accessdrugs1	Antibiotics to treat animals	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
accessdrugs2	Other Veterinary drugs to treat animals	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
accessdrugs3	Veterinary vaccinatons	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
		<table border="1"> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </table>				

abxusedur	How long do you use antibiotic drugs for	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>as advised</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>until animal is cured</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>until the package is empty</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>as long as I can afford</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>one time treatment</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>continuously over an extended period</td></tr> </table>	1	as advised	2	until animal is cured	3	until the package is empty	4	as long as I can afford	5	one time treatment	6	continuously over an extended period
1	as advised													
2	until animal is cured													
3	until the package is empty													
4	as long as I can afford													
5	one time treatment													
6	continuously over an extended period													
expd	What do you do with expired veterinary drugs?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>dispose of</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>return to pharmacy</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>give to other farmer</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>use for intended treatment</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>nothing</td></tr> <tr><td>99</td><td>other</td></tr> </table>	1	dispose of	2	return to pharmacy	3	give to other farmer	4	use for intended treatment	5	nothing	99	other
1	dispose of													
2	return to pharmacy													
3	give to other farmer													
4	use for intended treatment													
5	nothing													
99	other													
expdo	Please specify what you do with expired drugs	User entered text												
vacdo	What do vaccinations do?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>cure sick animals</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>prevent animals from becoming sick</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>cure sick animals and prevent animals from becoming sick</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>fattening</td></tr> <tr><td>99</td><td>other</td></tr> </table>	1	cure sick animals	2	prevent animals from becoming sick	3	cure sick animals and prevent animals from becoming sick	4	fattening	99	other		
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2	prevent animals from becoming sick													
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99	other													
vacdo	Please specify what vaccinations do	User entered text												
abxdo	What do antibiotics do?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>cure sick animals</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>prevent animals from becoming sick</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>cure sick animals and prevent animals from becoming sick</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>fattening</td></tr> <tr><td>99</td><td>other</td></tr> </table>	1	cure sick animals	2	prevent animals from becoming sick	3	cure sick animals and prevent animals from becoming sick	4	fattening	99	other		
1	cure sick animals													
2	prevent animals from becoming sick													
3	cure sick animals and prevent animals from becoming sick													
4	fattening													
99	other													
abxdo	Please specify what antibiotics do	User entered text												

anvacc	Are any of the animals that you own vaccinated?	1	Yes
		0	No
vac	Hidden from user		
generated_table_list_label_1021	If yes, which species?	User entered text	
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_1022		1	Yes
		0	No
vacow	Cow	1	Yes
		0	No
vapig	Pig	1	Yes
		0	No
vashe	Sheep	1	Yes
		0	No
vagoat	Goat	1	Yes
		0	No
vadog	Dog	1	Yes
		0	No
vacat	Cat	1	Yes
		0	No
vahorse	Horse	1	Yes
		0	No
vadon	Donkey	1	Yes
		0	No
vachkn	Chicken	1	Yes
		0	No

vaother1	#{3}	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No						
1	Yes											
0	No											
vaother2	#{4}	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No						
1	Yes											
0	No											
vaother3	#{5}	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No						
1	Yes											
0	No											
vaccow	Hidden from user											
anvaccowwhat	What are cows vaccinated against?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Foot and mouth disease</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Lumpy skin disease</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Yes but unknown vaccine</td> </tr> </table>	1	Foot and mouth disease	2	Lumpy skin disease	3	Other	4	Yes but unknown vaccine		
1	Foot and mouth disease											
2	Lumpy skin disease											
3	Other											
4	Yes but unknown vaccine											
anvaccowfreq	How often are cows vaccinated?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Every 6 months</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Annually</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Biannually</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>One off</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	Every 6 months	2	Annually	3	Biannually	4	One off	9	Other
1	Every 6 months											
2	Annually											
3	Biannually											
4	One off											
9	Other											
antogvaccow	Are your cows brought together with other peoples'animals to vaccinate?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No						
1	Yes											
0	No											
anvaccowwho	Who carries out vaccinations?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Vet</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Animal Veterinary Officer</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Member of household</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Friend</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	Vet	2	Animal Veterinary Officer	3	Member of household	4	Friend	9	Other
1	Vet											
2	Animal Veterinary Officer											
3	Member of household											
4	Friend											
9	Other											
gycow	Hidden from user											
anvaccowwhattx	Please specify what cows are vaccinated against.	User entered text										

anvacccowfreq	Please specify how often cows are vaccinated.	User entered text										
anvacccowwho	Please specify who carries out cow vaccinations.	User entered text										
vacpig	Hidden from user											
anvaccpigwhat	What are pigs vaccinated against?	User entered text										
anvaccpigfreq	How often are pigs vaccinated?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Every 6 months</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Annually</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Biannually</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>One off</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Every 6 months	2	Annually	3	Biannually	4	One off	9	Other
1	Every 6 months											
2	Annually											
3	Biannually											
4	One off											
9	Other											
antogvaccpig	Are your pigs brought together with other peoples'animals to vaccinate?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No						
1	Yes											
0	No											
anvaccpigwho	Who carries out vaccinations?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Vet</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Animal Veterinary Officer</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Member of household</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Friend</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Vet	2	Animal Veterinary Officer	3	Member of household	4	Friend	9	Other
1	Vet											
2	Animal Veterinary Officer											
3	Member of household											
4	Friend											
9	Other											
gvpig	Hidden from user											
anvaccpigfreq	Please specify how often pigs are vaccinated.	User entered text										
anvaccpigwho	Please specify who carries out pig vaccinations.	User entered text										
vacsheep	Hidden from user											
anvaccsheewhat	What are sheep vaccinated against?	User entered text										
anvaccshefreq	How often are sheep vaccinated?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Every 6 months</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Annually</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Biannually</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>One off</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Every 6 months	2	Annually	3	Biannually	4	One off	9	Other
1	Every 6 months											
2	Annually											
3	Biannually											
4	One off											
9	Other											
antogvaccshe	Are your sheep brought together with other peoples'animals to vaccinate?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No						
1	Yes											
0	No											
anvaccshewho	Who carries out vaccinations?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Vet</td></tr> </table>	1	Vet								
1	Vet											

		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Animal Veterinary Officer</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Member of household</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Friend</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	2	Animal Veterinary Officer	3	Member of household	4	Friend	9	Other		
2	Animal Veterinary Officer											
3	Member of household											
4	Friend											
9	Other											
gvsheep	Hidden from user											
anvaccshefreqo	Please specify how often sheep are vaccinated.	User entered text										
anvaccshewhoo	Please specify who carries out sheep vaccinations.	User entered text										
vacgoat	Hidden from user											
anvacccoawhat	What are goats vaccinated against?	User entered text										
anvacccoafreq	How often are they vaccinated?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Every 6 months</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Annually</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Biannually</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>One off</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	Every 6 months	2	Annually	3	Biannually	4	One off	9	Other
1	Every 6 months											
2	Annually											
3	Biannually											
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antogvaccco	Are your goats brought together with other peoples' animals to vaccinate?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No						
1	Yes											
0	No											
anvacccoawho	Who carries out vaccinations?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Vet</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Animal Veterinary Officer</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Member of household</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Friend</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	Vet	2	Animal Veterinary Officer	3	Member of household	4	Friend	9	Other
1	Vet											
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3	Member of household											
4	Friend											
9	Other											
gvgoat	Hidden from user											
anvacccoafreqo	Please specify how often goats are vaccinated.	User entered text										
anvacccoawhoo	Please specify who carries out goat vaccinations.	User entered text										
vacdog	Hidden from user											
anvaccdogwhat	What are dogs vaccinated against?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Rabies</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Distemper</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Parvovirus</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	Rabies	2	Distemper	3	Parvovirus	4	Other		
1	Rabies											
2	Distemper											
3	Parvovirus											
4	Other											

anvaccdogfreq	How often are they vaccinated?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Every 6 months</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Annually</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Biannually</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>One off</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Every 6 months	2	Annually	3	Biannually	4	One off	9	Other
1	Every 6 months											
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3	Biannually											
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antogvaccdog	Are your dogs brought together with other peoples'animals to vaccinate?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No						
1	Yes											
0	No											
anvaccdogwho	Who carries out vaccinations?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Vet</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Animal Veterinary Officer</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Member of household</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Friend</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Vet	2	Animal Veterinary Officer	3	Member of household	4	Friend	9	Other
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4	Friend											
9	Other											
gvdog	Hidden from user											
anvaccdogwhattx	Please specify what dogs are vaccinated against.	User entered text										
anvaccdogfreqo	Please specify how often dogs are vaccinated.	User entered text										
anvaccdogwhoo	Please specify who carries out dog vaccinations.	User entered text										
vaccat	Hidden from user											
anvacccatwhat	What are cats vaccinated against?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Feline immunodeficiency virus</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Feline panleucopenia</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Rabies</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Feline immunodeficiency virus	2	Feline panleucopenia	4	Rabies	3	Other		
1	Feline immunodeficiency virus											
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4	Rabies											
3	Other											
anvacccatfreq	How often are they vaccinated?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Every 6 months</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Annually</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Biannually</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>One off</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Every 6 months	2	Annually	3	Biannually	4	One off	9	Other
1	Every 6 months											
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antogvacccat	Are your cats brought together with other peoples'animals to vaccinate?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No						
1	Yes											
0	No											

anvacccatwho	Who carries out vaccinations?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Vet</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Animal Veterinary Officer</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Member of household</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Friend</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Vet	2	Animal Veterinary Officer	3	Member of household	4	Friend	9	Other
1	Vet											
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3	Member of household											
4	Friend											
9	Other											
gvcat	Hidden from user											
anvacccatwhattx	Please specify what cats are vaccinated against.	User entered text										
anvacccatfreqo	Please specify how often cats are vaccinated.	User entered text										
anvacccatwhoo	Please specify who carries out cat vaccinations.	User entered text										
vachorse	Hidden from user											
anvacchorwhat	What are horses vaccinated against?	User entered text										
anvacchorfreq	How often are they vaccinated?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Every 6 months</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Annually</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Biannually</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>One off</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Every 6 months	2	Annually	3	Biannually	4	One off	9	Other
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4	One off											
9	Other											
anvacchorwho	Who carries out vaccinations?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No						
1	Yes											
0	No											
antogvacchor	Are your horses brought together with other peoples'animals to vaccinate?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Vet</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Animal Veterinary Officer</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Member of household</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Friend</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Vet	2	Animal Veterinary Officer	3	Member of household	4	Friend	9	Other
1	Vet											
2	Animal Veterinary Officer											
3	Member of household											
4	Friend											
9	Other											
gvhorse	Hidden from user											
anvacchorfreqo	Please specify how often horses are vaccinated.	User entered text										
anvacchorwhoo	Please specify who carries out horse vaccinations.	User entered text										
vacdon	Hidden from user											
anvaccdonwhat	What are donkeys vaccinated against?	User entered text										
anvaccdonfreq	How often are they vaccinated?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Every 6 months</td></tr> </table>	1	Every 6 months								
1	Every 6 months											

		<table border="1"> <tr><td>2</td><td>Annually</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Biannually</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>One off</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	2	Annually	3	Biannually	4	One off	9	Other		
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antogvaccdon	Are your donkeys brought together with other peoples'animals to vaccinate?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No						
1	Yes											
0	No											
anvaccdonwho	Who carries out vaccinations?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Vet</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Animal Veterinary Officer</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Member of household</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Friend</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Vet	2	Animal Veterinary Officer	3	Member of household	4	Friend	9	Other
1	Vet											
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4	Friend											
9	Other											
gvdon	Hidden from user											
anvaccdonfreqo	Please specify how often donkeys are vaccinated.	User entered text										
anvaccdonwhoo	Please specify who carries out donkey vaccinations.	User entered text										
vacchk	Hidden from user											
anvaccchiwhat	What are chickens vaccinated against?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Newcastle disease</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Newcastle disease	2	Other						
1	Newcastle disease											
2	Other											
anvacccchifreq	How often are they vaccinated?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Every 6 months</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Annually</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Biannually</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>One off</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Every 6 months	2	Annually	3	Biannually	4	One off	9	Other
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antogvacccchi	Are your chickens brought together with other peoples'animals to vaccinate?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No						
1	Yes											
0	No											
anvacccchiwho	Who carries out vaccinations?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Vet</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Animal Veterinary Officer</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Member of household</td></tr> </table>	1	Vet	2	Animal Veterinary Officer	3	Member of household				
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4	Friend											
9	Other											
gvchk	Hidden from user											
anvacchiwhattx	Please specify what chickens are vaccinated against.	User entered text										
anvacchifreq	Please specify how often chickens are vaccinated.	User entered text										
anvacchiwhoo	Please specify who carries out chicken vaccinations.	User entered text										
vacoth1	Hidden from user											
anvacoth1what	What are \${3} vaccinated against?	User entered text										
anvacoth1freq	How often are they vaccinated?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Every 6 months</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Annually</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Biannually</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>One off</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	Every 6 months	2	Annually	3	Biannually	4	One off	9	Other
1	Every 6 months											
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antogvacoth1	Are your animals brought together with other peoples'animals to vaccinate?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No						
1	Yes											
0	No											
anvacoth1who	Who carries out vaccinations?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Vet</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Animal Veterinary Officer</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Member of household</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Friend</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	Vet	2	Animal Veterinary Officer	3	Member of household	4	Friend	9	Other
1	Vet											
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4	Friend											
9	Other											
gvohr1	Hidden from user											
anvacoth1freq	Please specify how often \${3} are vaccinated.	User entered text										
anvacoth1whoo	Please specify who carries out \${3} vaccinations.	User entered text										
vacoth2	Hidden from user											
anvacoth2what	What are \${4} vaccinated against?	User entered text										
anvacoth2freq	How often are they vaccinated?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Every 6 months</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Annually</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Biannually</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>One off</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	Every 6 months	2	Annually	3	Biannually	4	One off	9	Other
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antogvaccoth2	Are your animals brought together with other peoples'animals to vaccinate?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No						
1	Yes											
0	No											
anvaccoth2who	Who carries out vaccinations?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Vet</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Animal Veterinary Officer</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Member of household</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Friend</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	Vet	2	Animal Veterinary Officer	3	Member of household	4	Friend	9	Other
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gvohr2	Hidden from user											
anvaccoth2freqo	Please specify how often \${4} are vaccinated.	User entered text										
anvaccoth2whoo	Please specify who carries out \${4} vaccinations.	User entered text										
vacoth3	Hidden from user											
anvaccoth3what	What are \${5} vaccinated against?	User entered text										
anvaccoth3freq	How often are they vaccinated?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Every 6 months</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Annually</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Biannually</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>One off</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	Every 6 months	2	Annually	3	Biannually	4	One off	9	Other
1	Every 6 months											
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3	Biannually											
4	One off											
9	Other											
antogvaccoth3	Are your animals brought together with other peoples'animals to vaccinate?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No						
1	Yes											
0	No											
anvaccoth3who	Who carries out vaccinations?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Vet</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Animal Veterinary Officer</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Member of household</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Friend</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	Vet	2	Animal Veterinary Officer	3	Member of household	4	Friend	9	Other
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gvohr3	Hidden from user											
anvaccoth3freqo	Please specify how often \${5} are vaccinated.	User entered text										
anvaccoth3whoo	Please specify who carries out \${5} vaccinations.	User entered text										
paratogwhi	Are animals brought together to administer anti-parasite	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes								
1	Yes											

	treatment?	0	No
grpAntiParasite	Hidden from user		
paratogspp	Which species of animals are brought together to administer anti-parasite treatment?	User entered text	
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_1162		1	Yes
		0	No
paratocow	Cow	1	Yes
		0	No
paratopig	Pig	1	Yes
		0	No
paratoshe	Sheep	1	Yes
		0	No
paratogoat	Goat	1	Yes
		0	No
paratodog	Dog	1	Yes
		0	No
paratocat	Cat	1	Yes
		0	No
paratohor	Horse	1	Yes
		0	No
paratodon	Donkey	1	Yes
		0	No
paratochi	Chicken	1	Yes
		0	No

paratoo1	#{3}	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No						
1	Yes											
0	No											
paratoo2	#{4}	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No						
1	Yes											
0	No											
paratoo3	#{5}	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No						
1	Yes											
0	No											
grpAntiParasiteFreq	Hidden from user											
paratooftcow	How often are cows brought together to administer anti-parasite treatment?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Every 6 months</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Annually</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Biannually</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>One off</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	Every 6 months	2	Annually	3	Biannually	4	One off	9	Other
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paratooftpig	How often are pigs brought together to administer anti-parasite treatment?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Every 6 months</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Annually</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Biannually</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>One off</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	Every 6 months	2	Annually	3	Biannually	4	One off	9	Other
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paratooftshe	How often are sheeps brought together to administer anti-parasite treatment?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Every 6 months</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Annually</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Biannually</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>One off</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	Every 6 months	2	Annually	3	Biannually	4	One off	9	Other
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paratooftgoa	How often are goats brought together to administer anti-parasite treatment?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Every 6 months</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Annually</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Biannually</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>One off</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	Every 6 months	2	Annually	3	Biannually	4	One off	9	Other
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paratooftdog	How often are dogs brought together to administer anti-parasite	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Every 6 months</td> </tr> </table>	1	Every 6 months								
1	Every 6 months											

	treatment?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>2</td><td>Annually</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Biannually</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>One off</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	2	Annually	3	Biannually	4	One off	9	Other		
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paratooftcat	How often are cats brought together to administer anti-parasite treatment?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Every 6 months</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Annually</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Biannually</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>One off</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Every 6 months	2	Annually	3	Biannually	4	One off	9	Other
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paratooffhor	How often are horse brought together to administer anti-parasite treatment?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Every 6 months</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Annually</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Biannually</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>One off</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Every 6 months	2	Annually	3	Biannually	4	One off	9	Other
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paratooftdon	How often are donkey brought together to administer anti-parasite treatment?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Every 6 months</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Annually</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Biannually</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>One off</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Every 6 months	2	Annually	3	Biannually	4	One off	9	Other
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paratooftchi	How often are chicken brought together to administer anti-parasite treatment?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Every 6 months</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Annually</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Biannually</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>One off</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Every 6 months	2	Annually	3	Biannually	4	One off	9	Other
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paratooftoth1	How often are \${3} brought together to administer anti-parasite treatment?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Every 6 months</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Annually</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Biannually</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>One off</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Every 6 months	2	Annually	3	Biannually	4	One off	9	Other
1	Every 6 months											
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3	Biannually											
4	One off											
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paratooftoth2	How often are \${4} brought together to administer anti-parasite treatment?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Every 6 months</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Annually</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Biannually</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>One off</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Every 6 months	2	Annually	3	Biannually	4	One off	9	Other
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paratooftoth3	How often are \${5} brought together to administer anti-parasite treatment?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Every 6 months</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Annually</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Biannually</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>One off</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Every 6 months	2	Annually	3	Biannually	4	One off	9	Other
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3	Biannually											
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9	Other											
grpAntiParasiteFreqo	Hidden from user											
paratooftcowo	Please specify how often cows are brought together to administer anti-parasite treatment?	User entered text										
paratooftpigo	Please specify how often pigs are brought together to administer anti-parasite treatment?	User entered text										
paratooftsheo	Please specify how often sheeps are brought together to administer anti-parasite treatment?	User entered text										
paratooftgoao	Please specify how often goats are brought together to administer anti-parasite treatment?	User entered text										
paratooftdogo	Please specify how often dogs are brought together to administer anti-parasite treatment?	User entered text										
paratooftcato	Please specify how often cats are brought together to administer anti-parasite treatment?	User entered text										
paratooffthoro	Please specify how often horse are brought together to administer anti-parasite treatment?	User entered text										
paratooftdono	Please specify how often donkey are brought together to administer anti-parasite treatment?	User entered text										
paratooftchio	Please specify how often chicken are brought together to administer anti-parasite treatment?	User entered text										
paratooftohn1	Please specify how often \${3} are brought together to administer anti-parasite treatment?	User entered text										
paratooftohn2	Please specify how often \${4} are brought together to administer anti-parasite treatment?	User entered text										
paratooftohn3	Please specify how often \${5} are brought together to administer anti-parasite treatment?	User entered text										
isolsic	When an animal is sick, do you separate it from the healthy animals?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No						
1	Yes											
0	No											

		2	Unknown
isolsichow	How do you achieve this?	1	Separate krall
		2	Slaughter sick animals
		3	Sell sick animals
		4	Move animal to another household
		99	Other
isolsichowt	Please specify other	User entered text	
grpSectionI	Hidden from user		
grpCowAntibiotic	Hidden from user		
aban0	Which antibiotics have been used by Cow in the household over the last six months	User entered text	
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_1210		1	Yes
		0	No
cowtetracycline	Tetracycline	1	Yes
		0	No
cowstreptomycin	Streptomycin	1	Yes
		0	No
cowampicilin	Ampicillin	1	Yes
		0	No
cowamox	Amoxicillin-clavulanate	1	Yes
		0	No
cowtrimetho	Trimethoprim sulphonamide	1	Yes
		0	No
cowothrabx	Other	1	Yes
		0	No

cowunknown	Unknown	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
cowothrabxt	Specify other antibiotic	User entered text				
aban0paccow	Picture of packet	User captured image				
aban0descow	Description of packet	User entered text				
grpPigAntibiotic	Hidden from user					
aban1	Which antibiotics have been used by Pig in the household over the last six months	User entered text				
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_1223		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
pigtetracycline	Tetracycline	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
pigstreptomycin	Streptomycin	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
pigampicilin	Ampicillin	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
pigamox	Amoxicillin-clavulanate	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
pigtrimetho	Trimethoprim sulphonamide	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
pigothrabx	Other	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
pigunknown	Unknown	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
pigothrabxt	Specify other antibiotic	User entered text				
aban0pacpig	Picture of packet	User captured image				

aban0descpig	Description of packet	User entered text				
grpSheepAntibiotic	Hidden from user					
generated_note_name_1235	Which antibiotics have been used by Sheep in the household over the last six months	User entered text				
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_1236		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
sheeptetracycline	Tetracycline	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
sheepstreptomycin	Streptomycin	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
sheepampicilin	Ampicillin	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
sheepamox	Amoxicillin-clavulanate	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
sheeptrimetho	Trimethoprim sulphonamide	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
sheepothrabx	Other	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
sheepunknown	Unknown	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
sheepothrabxt	Specify other antibiotic	User entered text				
aban0pacshe	picture of packet	User captured image				
aban0descshe	Description of packet	User entered text				
grpGoatAntibiotic	Hidden from user					
generated_note_name_1248	Which antibiotics have been used by Goat in the household over the last six months	User entered text				
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_1249		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes		
1	Yes					

		0	No
goattetracycline	Tetracycline	1	Yes
		0	No
goatstreptomycin	Streptomycin	1	Yes
		0	No
goatampicilin	Ampicillin	1	Yes
		0	No
goatamox	Amoxicillin-clavulanate	1	Yes
		0	No
goatrimetho	Trimethoprim sulphonamide	1	Yes
		0	No
goatothrabx	Other	1	Yes
		0	No
goatunknown	Unknown	1	Yes
		0	No
goatothrabxt	Specify other antibiotic	User entered text	
aban0pacgoa	picture of packet	User captured image	
aban0descgoa	Description of packet	User entered text	
grpDogAntibiotic	Hidden from user		
generated_note_name_1261	Which antibiotics have been used by Dog in the household over the last six months	User entered text	
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_1262		1	Yes
		0	No
dogtetracycline	Tetracycline	1	Yes
		0	No

dogstreptomycin	Streptomycin	1	Yes
		0	No
dogampicilin	Ampicillin	1	Yes
		0	No
dogamox	Amoxicillin-clavulanate	1	Yes
		0	No
dogtrimetho	Trimethoprim sulphonamide	1	Yes
		0	No
dogothrabx	Other	1	Yes
		0	No
dogunknown	Unknown	1	Yes
		0	No
dogothrabxt	Specify other antibiotic	User entered text	
aban0pacdog	picture of packet	User captured image	
aban0descdog	Description of packet	User entered text	
grpCatAntibiotic	Hidden from user		
generated_note_name_1274	Which antibiotics have been used by cat in the household over the last six months	User entered text	
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_1275		1	Yes
		0	No
cattetracycline	Tetracycline	1	Yes
		0	No
catstreptomycin	Streptomycin	1	Yes
		0	No
catampicilin	Ampicillin	1	Yes
		0	No

catamox	Amoxicillin-clavulanate	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
catrimetho	Trimethoprim sulphonamide	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
catothrabx	Other	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
catunknown	Unknown	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
catothrabxt	Specify other antibiotic	User entered text				
aban0paccat	picture of packet	User captured image				
aban0descat	Description of packet	User entered text				
grpHorseAntibiotic	Hidden from user					
generated_note_name_1287	Which antibiotics have been used by horse in the household over the last six months	User entered text				
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_1288		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
horsetetracycline	Tetracycline	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
horsestreptomycin	Streptomycin	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
horseampicilin	Ampicillin	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
horseamox	Amoxicillin-clavulanate	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
horsetrimetho	Trimethoprim sulphonamide	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes		
1	Yes					

		0	No
horseothrabx	Other	1	Yes
		0	No
horseunknown	Unknown	1	Yes
		0	No
horseothrabxt	Specify other antibiotic	User entered text	
aban0pachor	picture of packet	User captured image	
aban0deschor	Description of packet	User entered text	
grpDonkeyAntibiotic	Hidden from user		
generated_note_name_1300	Which antibiotics have been used by donkey in the household over the last six months	User entered text	
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_1301		1	Yes
		0	No
donkeytetracycline	Tetracycline	1	Yes
		0	No
donkeystreptomycin	Streptomycin	1	Yes
		0	No
donkeyampicilin	Ampicillin	1	Yes
		0	No
donkeyamox	Amoxicillin-clavulanate	1	Yes
		0	No
donkeytrimetho	Trimethoprim sulphonamide	1	Yes
		0	No
donkeyothrabx	Other	1	Yes
		0	No

donkeyunknown	Unknown	1	Yes
		0	No
donkeyothrabxt	Specify other antibiotic	User entered text	
aban0pacdon	picture of packet	User captured image	
aban0descdon	Description of packet	User entered text	
grpChiAntibiotic	Hidden from user		
generated_note_name_1313	Which antibiotics have been used by chicken in the household over the last six months	User entered text	
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_1314		1	Yes
		0	No
chickentetracycline	Tetracycline	1	Yes
		0	No
chickenstreptomycin	Streptomycin	1	Yes
		0	No
chickenampicilin	Ampicillin	1	Yes
		0	No
chickenamox	Amoxicillin-clavulanate	1	Yes
		0	No
chickentrimetho	Trimethoprim sulphonamide	1	Yes
		0	No
chickenothrabx	Other	1	Yes
		0	No
chickenunknown	Unknown	1	Yes
		0	No
chickenothrabxt	Specify other antibiotic	User entered text	
aban0pacchi	picture of packet	User captured image	

aban0descchi	Description of packet	User entered text				
grpOther1Antibiotic	Hidden from user					
generated_note_name_1326	Which antibiotics have been used by \${3} in the household over the last six months	User entered text				
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_1327		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
other1tetracycline	Tetracycline	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
other1streptomycin	Streptomycin	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
other1ampicilin	Ampicillin	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
other1amox	Amoxicillin-clavulanate	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
other1trimetho	Trimethoprim sulphonamide	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
othr1abx	Other	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
other1unknown	Unknown	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
othr1abxt	Specify other antibiotic	User entered text				
aban10paco	picture of packet	User captured image				
aban10desc	Description of packet	User entered text				
grpOther2Antibiotic	Hidden from user					
generated_note_name_1339	Which antibiotics have been used by \${4} in the household over the last six months	User entered text				
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_1340		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes		
1	Yes					

		0	No
other2tetracycline	Tetracycline	1	Yes
		0	No
other2streptomycin	Streptomycin	1	Yes
		0	No
other2ampicilin	Ampicillin	1	Yes
		0	No
other2amox	Amoxicillin-clavulanate	1	Yes
		0	No
other2trimetho	Trimethoprim sulphonamide	1	Yes
		0	No
othr2abx	Other	1	Yes
		0	No
other2unknown	Unknown	1	Yes
		0	No
othr2abxt	Specify other antibiotic	User entered text	
aban20paco	picture of packet	User captured image	
aban20desc	Description of packet	User entered text	
grpOther3Antibiotic	Hidden from user		
generated_note_name_1352	Which antibiotics have been used by \${5} in the household over the last six months	User entered text	
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_1353		1	Yes
		0	No
other3tetracycline	Tetracycline	1	Yes
		0	No

other3streptomycin	Streptomycin	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No										
1	Yes															
0	No															
other3ampicilin	Ampicillin	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No										
1	Yes															
0	No															
other3amox	Amoxicillin-clavulanate	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No										
1	Yes															
0	No															
other3trimetho	Trimethoprim sulphonamide	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No										
1	Yes															
0	No															
othr3abx	Other	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No										
1	Yes															
0	No															
other3unknown	Unknown	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No										
1	Yes															
0	No															
othr3abxt	Specify other antibiotic	User entered text														
aban30paco	picture of packet	User captured image														
aban30desc	Description of packet	User entered text														
grpAntBioSource	Hidden from user															
abwherefrom0	Where do the antibiotics used to treat animals in the household come from?	User entered text														
abwherefrom0cow	Cow	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Vet</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Animal Veterinary Officer</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Friend</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Pharmacy</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Other drug seller</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>Family stock (saved)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	Vet	2	Animal Veterinary Officer	3	Friend	4	Pharmacy	5	Other drug seller	6	Family stock (saved)	7	Other
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4	Pharmacy															
5	Other drug seller															
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abwherefrom0pig	Pig	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Vet</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Animal Veterinary Officer</td> </tr> </table>	1	Vet	2	Animal Veterinary Officer										
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5	Other drug seller															
6	Family stock (saved)															
7	Other															
abwherefrom0she	Sheep	<table border="1"> <tbody> <tr><td>1</td><td>Vet</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Animal Veterinary Officer</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Friend</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Pharmacy</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Other drug seller</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Family stock (saved)</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>Other</td></tr> </tbody> </table>	1	Vet	2	Animal Veterinary Officer	3	Friend	4	Pharmacy	5	Other drug seller	6	Family stock (saved)	7	Other
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7	Other															
abwherefrom0goa	Goat	<table border="1"> <tbody> <tr><td>1</td><td>Vet</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Animal Veterinary Officer</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Friend</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Pharmacy</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Other drug seller</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Family stock (saved)</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>Other</td></tr> </tbody> </table>	1	Vet	2	Animal Veterinary Officer	3	Friend	4	Pharmacy	5	Other drug seller	6	Family stock (saved)	7	Other
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3	Friend															
4	Pharmacy															
5	Other drug seller															
6	Family stock (saved)															
7	Other															
abwherefrom0dog	Dog	<table border="1"> <tbody> <tr><td>1</td><td>Vet</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Animal Veterinary Officer</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Friend</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Pharmacy</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Other drug seller</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Family stock (saved)</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>Other</td></tr> </tbody> </table>	1	Vet	2	Animal Veterinary Officer	3	Friend	4	Pharmacy	5	Other drug seller	6	Family stock (saved)	7	Other
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2	Animal Veterinary Officer															
3	Friend															
4	Pharmacy															
5	Other drug seller															
6	Family stock (saved)															
7	Other															
abwherefrom0cat	Cat	<table border="1"> <tbody> <tr><td>1</td><td>Vet</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Animal Veterinary Officer</td></tr> </tbody> </table>	1	Vet	2	Animal Veterinary Officer										
1	Vet															
2	Animal Veterinary Officer															

		<table border="1"> <tr><td>3</td><td>Friend</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Pharmacy</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Other drug seller</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Family stock (saved)</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	3	Friend	4	Pharmacy	5	Other drug seller	6	Family stock (saved)	7	Other				
3	Friend															
4	Pharmacy															
5	Other drug seller															
6	Family stock (saved)															
7	Other															
abwherefrom0hor	Horse	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Vet</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Animal Veterinary Officer</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Friend</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Pharmacy</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Other drug seller</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Family stock (saved)</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Vet	2	Animal Veterinary Officer	3	Friend	4	Pharmacy	5	Other drug seller	6	Family stock (saved)	7	Other
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4	Pharmacy															
5	Other drug seller															
6	Family stock (saved)															
7	Other															
abwherefrom0don	Donkey	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Vet</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Animal Veterinary Officer</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Friend</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Pharmacy</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Other drug seller</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Family stock (saved)</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Vet	2	Animal Veterinary Officer	3	Friend	4	Pharmacy	5	Other drug seller	6	Family stock (saved)	7	Other
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2	Animal Veterinary Officer															
3	Friend															
4	Pharmacy															
5	Other drug seller															
6	Family stock (saved)															
7	Other															
abwherefrom0bir	Chicken	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Vet</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Animal Veterinary Officer</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Friend</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Pharmacy</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Other drug seller</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Family stock (saved)</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Vet	2	Animal Veterinary Officer	3	Friend	4	Pharmacy	5	Other drug seller	6	Family stock (saved)	7	Other
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4	Pharmacy															
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abwherefrom0oth1	#{3}	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Vet</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Animal Veterinary Officer</td></tr> </table>	1	Vet	2	Animal Veterinary Officer										
1	Vet															
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3	Friend															
4	Pharmacy															
5	Other drug seller															
6	Family stock (saved)															
7	Other															
abwherefrom0oth2	\$(4)	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Vet</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Animal Veterinary Officer</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Friend</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Pharmacy</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Other drug seller</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Family stock (saved)</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Vet	2	Animal Veterinary Officer	3	Friend	4	Pharmacy	5	Other drug seller	6	Family stock (saved)	7	Other
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6	Family stock (saved)															
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abwherefrom0oth3	\$(5)	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Vet</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Animal Veterinary Officer</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Friend</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Pharmacy</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Other drug seller</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Family stock (saved)</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Vet	2	Animal Veterinary Officer	3	Friend	4	Pharmacy	5	Other drug seller	6	Family stock (saved)	7	Other
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4	Pharmacy															
5	Other drug seller															
6	Family stock (saved)															
7	Other															
grpAntBioSourceo	Hidden from user															
abwherefrom0cowo	Please specify where antibiotics for Cows come from	User entered text														
abwherefrom0pigo	Please specify where antibiotics for Pigs come from	User entered text														
abwherefrom0sheo	Please specify where antibiotics for Sheeps come from	User entered text														
abwherefrom0goao	Please specify where antibiotics for Goats come from	User entered text														
abwherefrom0dogo	Please specify where antibiotics for Dogs come from	User entered text														
abwherefrom0cato	Please specify where antibiotics for Cats come from	User entered text														
abwherefrom0horo	Please specify where antibiotics for Horses come from	User entered text														
abwherefrom0dono	Please specify where antibiotics for Donkeys come from	User entered text														
abwherefrom0biro	Please specify where antibiotics for Chickens come from	User entered text														
abwherefrom0otho1	Please specify where antibiotics for \$(3) come from	User entered text														
abwherefrom0otho2	Please specify where antibiotics for \$(4) come from	User entered text														

abwherefrom0otho3	Please specify where antibiotics for \${5} come from	User entered text												
waittr	Hidden from user													
abwd0	How long after antibiotic treatment do you wait to consume, slaughter or sell animal products? (Days)	User entered text												
abwd0cow	How long after antibiotic treatment do you wait to consume, slaughter or sell Cow products	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1 day</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>1 week</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>1 month</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Longer</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Do not wait</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	1 day	2	1 week	3	1 month	4	Longer	5	Do not wait	6	Other
1	1 day													
2	1 week													
3	1 month													
4	Longer													
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6	Other													
abwd0howcow	How was this period decided?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>No reason</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Advice from vet</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Advice from Animal Veterinary Officer</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Advice from pharmacist</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Other (free text)</td></tr> </table>	1	No reason	2	Don't know	3	Advice from vet	4	Advice from Animal Veterinary Officer	5	Advice from pharmacist	6	Other (free text)
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2	Don't know													
3	Advice from vet													
4	Advice from Animal Veterinary Officer													
5	Advice from pharmacist													
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abwd0pig	How long after antibiotic treatment do you wait to consume, slaughter or sell Pig products	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1 day</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>1 week</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>1 month</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Longer</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Do not wait</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	1 day	2	1 week	3	1 month	4	Longer	5	Do not wait	6	Other
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5	Advice from pharmacist													
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abwd0she	How long after antibiotic treatment do you wait to consume, slaughter or sell Sheep products	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1 day</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>1 week</td></tr> </table>	1	1 day	2	1 week								
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abwd0howshe	How was this period decided?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>No reason</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Don't know</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Advice from vet</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Advice from Animal Veterinary Officer</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Advice from pharmacist</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Other (free text)</td></tr> </table>	1	No reason	2	Don't know	3	Advice from vet	4	Advice from Animal Veterinary Officer	5	Advice from pharmacist	6	Other (free text)
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abwd0goa	How long after antibiotic treatment do you wait to consume, slaughter or sell Goat products	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1 day</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>1 week</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>1 month</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Longer</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Do not wait</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	1 day	2	1 week	3	1 month	4	Longer	5	Do not wait	6	Other
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abwd0hor	How long after antibiotic treatment do you wait to consume, slaughter or sell Horse products	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1 day</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>1 week</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>1 month</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Longer</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Do not wait</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	1 day	2	1 week	3	1 month	4	Longer	5	Do not wait	6	Other
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abwd0don	How long after antibiotic treatment do you wait to consume, slaughter or sell Donkey products	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1 day</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>1 week</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>1 month</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Longer</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Do not wait</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	1 day	2	1 week	3	1 month	4	Longer	5	Do not wait	6	Other
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abwd0chi	How long after antibiotic treatment do you wait to consume, slaughter or sell Chicken products	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1 day</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>1 week</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>1 month</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Longer</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Do not wait</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	1 day	2	1 week	3	1 month	4	Longer	5	Do not wait	6	Other
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abwd0oth1	How long after antibiotic treatment do you wait to consume, slaughter or sell \${3} products	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1 day</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>1 week</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>1 month</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Longer</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Do not wait</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	1 day	2	1 week	3	1 month	4	Longer	5	Do not wait	6	Other
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abwd0oth2	How long after antibiotic treatment do you wait to consume, slaughter or sell \${4} products	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1 day</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>1 week</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>1 month</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Longer</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Do not wait</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	1 day	2	1 week	3	1 month	4	Longer	5	Do not wait	6	Other
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abwd0oth3	How long after antibiotic treatment do you wait to consume, slaughter or sell \${5} products	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>1 day</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>1 week</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>1 month</td></tr> <tr><td></td><td></td></tr> </table>	1	1 day	2	1 week	3	1 month						
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abwd0howoth3	How was this period decided?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>No reason</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Advice from vet</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Advice from Animal Veterinary Officer</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Advice from pharmacist</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>Other (free text)</td> </tr> </table>	1	No reason	2	Don't know	3	Advice from vet	4	Advice from Animal Veterinary Officer	5	Advice from pharmacist	6	Other (free text)
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waittro	Hidden from user													
oabwd0cow	Please specify how long after antibiotic treatment do you wait to consume, slaughter or sell Cow products	User entered text												
abwd0howcowo	Please specify how this waiting period for cows was decided?	User entered text												
oabwd0pig	Please specify how long after antibiotic treatment do you wait to consume, slaughter or sell Pig products	User entered text												
abwd0howpigo	Please specify how this waiting period for pigs was decided?	User entered text												
oabwd0she	Please specify how long after antibiotic treatment do you wait to consume, slaughter or sell Sheep products	User entered text												
abwd0sheo	Please specify how this waiting period for sheep was decided?	User entered text												
oabwd0goa	Please specify how long after antibiotic treatment do you wait to consume, slaughter or sell Goat products	User entered text												
abwd0howgoao	Please specify how this waiting period for goats was decided?	User entered text												
oabwd0hor	Please specify how long after antibiotic treatment do you wait to consume, slaughter or sell Horse products	User entered text												
abwd0howhoro	Please specify how this waiting period for horses was decided?	User entered text												
oabwd0don	Please specify how long after antibiotic treatment do you wait to consume, slaughter or sell Donkey products	User entered text												
abwd0howdono	Please specify how this waiting period for donkeys was decided?	User entered text												
oabwd0chi	Please specify how long after antibiotic treatment do you wait to consume, slaughter or sell Chicken products	User entered text												
abwd0howchio	Please specify how this waiting period for chickens was decided?	User entered text												
oabwd0oth1	Please specify how long after antibiotic treatment do you wait to consume, slaughter or sell \${3} products	User entered text												
abwd0howoth1o	Please specify how this waiting period for \${3} was decided?	User entered text												
oabwd0oth2	Please specify how long after antibiotic treatment do you wait to	User entered text												

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abwd0howoth2o	Please specify how this waiting period for \${4} was decided?	User entered text																				
oabwd0oth3	Please specify how long after antibiotic treatment do you wait to consume, slaughter or sell \${5} products	User entered text																				
abwd0howoth3o	Please specify how this waiting period for \${5} was decided?	User entered text																				
grpSymptoms	Hidden from user																					
sympab0	What are the most common symptoms/diseases which you have treated with antibiotics over the last 12 months in animals?	User entered text																				
sympab0cow	Cow	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Pneumonia</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Skin problem</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Abscess</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>TB</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Foot and mouth</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Cough</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>Diarrhoea</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>Lameness</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>Other</td></tr> <tr><td>10</td><td>None</td></tr> </table>	1	Pneumonia	2	Skin problem	3	Abscess	4	TB	5	Foot and mouth	6	Cough	7	Diarrhoea	8	Lameness	9	Other	10	None
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sympab0pig	Pig	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Pneumonia</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Skin problem</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Abscess</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>TB</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Cough</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>Diarrhoea</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>Lameness</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>Other</td></tr> <tr><td>10</td><td>None</td></tr> </table>	1	Pneumonia	2	Skin problem	3	Abscess	4	TB	6	Cough	7	Diarrhoea	8	Lameness	9	Other	10	None		
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sympab0she	Sheep	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Pneumonia</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Skin problem</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Abscess</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>TB</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Foot and mouth</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Cough</td></tr> </table>	1	Pneumonia	2	Skin problem	3	Abscess	4	TB	5	Foot and mouth	6	Cough								
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		10	None
sympab0goa	Goat	1	Pneumonia
		2	Skin problem
		3	Abscess
		4	TB
		5	Foot and mouth
		6	Cough
		7	Diarrhoea
		8	Lameness
		9	Other
		10	None
sympab0dog	Dog	1	Pneumonia
		2	Skin problem
		3	Abscess
		6	Cough
		7	Diarrhoea
		8	Lameness
		9	Other
		10	None
sympab0cat	Cat	1	Pneumonia
		2	Skin problem
		3	Abscess
		4	TB
		5	Foot and mouth
		6	Cough
		7	Diarrhoea
		8	Lameness
		9	Other
		10	None

sympab0hor	Horse	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Pneumonia</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Skin problem</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Abscess</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>TB</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Foot and mouth</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Cough</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>Diarrhoea</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>Lameness</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>Other</td></tr> <tr><td>10</td><td>None</td></tr> </table>	1	Pneumonia	2	Skin problem	3	Abscess	4	TB	5	Foot and mouth	6	Cough	7	Diarrhoea	8	Lameness	9	Other	10	None
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sympab0don	Donkey	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Pneumonia</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Skin problem</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Abscess</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>TB</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Foot and mouth</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Cough</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>Diarrhoea</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>Lameness</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>Other</td></tr> <tr><td>10</td><td>None</td></tr> </table>	1	Pneumonia	2	Skin problem	3	Abscess	4	TB	5	Foot and mouth	6	Cough	7	Diarrhoea	8	Lameness	9	Other	10	None
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sympab0bir	Chicken	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Pneumonia</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Skin problem</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Abscess</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Cough</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>Diarrhoea</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>Lameness</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>Other</td></tr> <tr><td>10</td><td>None</td></tr> </table>	1	Pneumonia	2	Skin problem	3	Abscess	6	Cough	7	Diarrhoea	8	Lameness	9	Other	10	None				
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sympab0oth2	#{4}	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Pneumonia</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Skin problem</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Abscess</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>TB</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Cough</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>Diarrhoea</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>Lameness</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>Other</td></tr> <tr><td>10</td><td>None</td></tr> </table>	1	Pneumonia	2	Skin problem	3	Abscess	4	TB	6	Cough	7	Diarrhoea	8	Lameness	9	Other	10	None
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sympab0oth3	#{5}	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Pneumonia</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Skin problem</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Abscess</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>TB</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Cough</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>Diarrhoea</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>Lameness</td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>Other</td></tr> <tr><td>10</td><td>None</td></tr> </table>	1	Pneumonia	2	Skin problem	3	Abscess	4	TB	6	Cough	7	Diarrhoea	8	Lameness	9	Other	10	None
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grpSymptomso	Hidden from user																			
sympab0cowo	Please specify what are the most common symptoms/diseases which you have treated Cows with antibiotics over the last 12 months?	User entered text																		
sympab0pigo	Please specify what are the most common symptoms/diseases which you have treated Pigs with antibiotics over the last 12 months?	User entered text																		
sympab0sheo	Please specify what are the most common symptoms/diseases which you have treated Sheeps with antibiotics over the last 12 months?	User entered text																		

sympab0goao	Please specify what are the most common symptoms/diseases which you have treated Goats with antibiotics over the last 12 months?	User entered text				
sympab0dogo	Please specify what are the most common symptoms/diseases which you have treated Dogs with antibiotics over the last 12 months?	User entered text				
sympab0cato	Please specify what are the most common symptoms/diseases which you have treated Cats with antibiotics over the last 12 months?	User entered text				
sympab0horo	Please specify what are the most common symptoms/diseases which you have treated Horses with antibiotics over the last 12 months?	User entered text				
sympab0dono	Please specify what are the most common symptoms/diseases which you have treated Donkeys with antibiotics over the last 12 months?	User entered text				
sympab0biro	Please specify what are the most common symptoms/diseases which you have treated Chickens with antibiotics over the last 12 months?	User entered text				
sympab0otho1	Please specify what are the most common symptoms/diseases which you have treated \${3} with antibiotics over the last 12 months?	User entered text				
sympab0otho2	Please specify what are the most common symptoms/diseases which you have treated \${4} with antibiotics over the last 12 months?	User entered text				
sympab0otho3	Please specify what are the most common symptoms/diseases which you have treated \${5} with antibiotics over the last 12 months?	User entered text				
grpAdjustAntibiotics	Hidden from user					
generated_note_name_1468	Do you adjust the dose of antibiotics according the weight of the animal	User entered text				
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_1469		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
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abdosad0cow	Cow	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
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abdosad0pig	Pig	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
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abdosad0she	Sheep	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
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abdosad0goa	Goat	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No						
1	Yes											
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abdosad0dog	Dog	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No						
1	Yes											
0	No											
abdosad0cat	Cat	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No						
1	Yes											
0	No											
abdosad0hor	Horse	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No						
1	Yes											
0	No											
abdosad0don	Donkey	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No						
1	Yes											
0	No											
abdosad0bir	Chicken	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No						
1	Yes											
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abdosad0oth1	\${3}	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No						
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abdosad0oth2	\${4}	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No						
1	Yes											
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abdosad0oth3	\${5}	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No						
1	Yes											
0	No											
grpAdjustAntibioticsHow	Hidden from user											
abdosad0cowhow	How do you estimate the size or weight of the cow to calculate dosage?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>By eye</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Use a chart</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Ask a vet</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Animal veterinarian officer</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Ask a pharmacist</td> </tr> </table>	1	By eye	2	Use a chart	3	Ask a vet	4	Animal veterinarian officer	5	Ask a pharmacist
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		6 Other												
abdosad0pighow	How do you estimate the size or weight of the pig to calculate dosage?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>By eye</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Use a chart</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Ask a vet</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Animal veteriary officer</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Ask a pharmacist</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	By eye	2	Use a chart	3	Ask a vet	4	Animal veteriary officer	5	Ask a pharmacist	6	Other
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abdosad0shehow	How do you estimate the size or weight of the sheep to calculate dosage?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>By eye</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Use a chart</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Ask a vet</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Animal veteriary officer</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Ask a pharmacist</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	By eye	2	Use a chart	3	Ask a vet	4	Animal veteriary officer	5	Ask a pharmacist	6	Other
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abdosad0goahow	How do you estimate the size or weight of the goat to calculate dosage?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>By eye</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Use a chart</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Ask a vet</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Animal veteriary officer</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Ask a pharmacist</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	By eye	2	Use a chart	3	Ask a vet	4	Animal veteriary officer	5	Ask a pharmacist	6	Other
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abdosad0doghow	How do you estimate the size or weight of the dog to calculate dosage?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>By eye</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Use a chart</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Ask a vet</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Animal veteriary officer</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Ask a pharmacist</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	By eye	2	Use a chart	3	Ask a vet	4	Animal veteriary officer	5	Ask a pharmacist	6	Other
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abdosad0cathow	How do you estimate the size or weight of the ca tto calculate dosage?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>By eye</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Use a chart</td></tr> </table>	1	By eye	2	Use a chart								
1	By eye													
2	Use a chart													

		<table border="1"> <tbody> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Ask a vet</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Animal veterinarian officer</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Ask a pharmacist</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	3	Ask a vet	4	Animal veterinarian officer	5	Ask a pharmacist	6	Other				
3	Ask a vet													
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5	Ask a pharmacist													
6	Other													
abdosad0horhow	How do you estimate the size or weight of the horse to calculate dosage?	<table border="1"> <tbody> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>By eye</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Use a chart</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Ask a vet</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Animal veterinarian officer</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Ask a pharmacist</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	1	By eye	2	Use a chart	3	Ask a vet	4	Animal veterinarian officer	5	Ask a pharmacist	6	Other
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abdosad0donhow	How do you estimate the size or weight of the donkey to calculate dosage?	<table border="1"> <tbody> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>By eye</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Use a chart</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Ask a vet</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Animal veterinarian officer</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Ask a pharmacist</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	1	By eye	2	Use a chart	3	Ask a vet	4	Animal veterinarian officer	5	Ask a pharmacist	6	Other
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abdosad0chihow	How do you estimate the size or weight of the chicken to calculate dosage?	<table border="1"> <tbody> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>By eye</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Use a chart</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Ask a vet</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Animal veterinarian officer</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Ask a pharmacist</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	1	By eye	2	Use a chart	3	Ask a vet	4	Animal veterinarian officer	5	Ask a pharmacist	6	Other
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abdosad0otherhow1	How do you estimate the size or weight of $\{3\}$ to calculate dosage?	<table border="1"> <tbody> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>By eye</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Use a chart</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Ask a vet</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Animal veterinarian officer</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Ask a pharmacist</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	1	By eye	2	Use a chart	3	Ask a vet	4	Animal veterinarian officer	5	Ask a pharmacist		
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		6 Other												
abdosad0otherhow2	How do you estimate the size or weight of \${4} to calculate dosage?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>By eye</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Use a chart</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Ask a vet</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Animal veterianry officer</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Ask a pharmacist</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	By eye	2	Use a chart	3	Ask a vet	4	Animal veterianry officer	5	Ask a pharmacist	6	Other
1	By eye													
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5	Ask a pharmacist													
6	Other													
abdosad0otherhow3	How do you estimate the size or weight of \${5} to calculate dosage?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>By eye</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Use a chart</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Ask a vet</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Animal veterianry officer</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Ask a pharmacist</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	By eye	2	Use a chart	3	Ask a vet	4	Animal veterianry officer	5	Ask a pharmacist	6	Other
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grpAdjustAntibioticsHowo	Hidden from user													
abdosad0cowhowo	Please specify how you estimate the size or weight of the cow to calculate dosage?	User entered text												
abdosad0pighowo	Please specify how you estimate the size or weight of the pig to calculate dosage?	User entered text												
abdosad0shehowo	Please specify how you estimate the size or weight of the sheep to calculate dosage?	User entered text												
abdosad0goahowo	Please specify how you estimate the size or weight of the goat to calculate dosage?	User entered text												
abdosad0doghowo	Please specify how you estimate the size or weight of the dog to calculate dosage?	User entered text												
abdosad0cathowo	Please specify how you estimate the size or weight of the ca tto calculate dosage?	User entered text												
abdosad0horhowo	Please specify how you estimate the size or weight of the horse to calculate dosage?	User entered text												
abdosad0donhowo	Please specify how you estimate the size or weight of the donkey to calculate dosage?	User entered text												
abdosad0chihowo	Please specify how you estimate the size or weight of the chicken to calculate dosage?	User entered text												
abdosad0otherhowo1	Please specify how you estimate the size or weight of \${3} to calculate dosage?	User entered text												

abdosad0otherhowo2	Please specify how you estimate the size or weight of \${4} to calculate dosage?	User entered text								
abdosad0otherhowo3	Please specify how you estimate the size or weight of \${5} to calculate dosage?	User entered text								
grpAdminAntibio	Hidden from user									
generated_note_name_1511	Over the last six months how have you administered antibiotics given to animals	User entered text								
admincow	Cow	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Injection</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>In feed</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>In water</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Injection	2	In feed	3	In water	4	Other
1	Injection									
2	In feed									
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4	Other									
adminpig	Pig	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Injection</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>In feed</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>In water</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Injection	2	In feed	3	In water	4	Other
1	Injection									
2	In feed									
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4	Other									
adminsheep	Sheep	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Injection</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>In feed</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>In water</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Injection	2	In feed	3	In water	4	Other
1	Injection									
2	In feed									
3	In water									
4	Other									
admingoat	Goat	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Injection</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>In feed</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>In water</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Injection	2	In feed	3	In water	4	Other
1	Injection									
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3	In water									
4	Other									
mindog	Dog	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Injection</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>In feed</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>In water</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Injection	2	In feed	3	In water	4	Other
1	Injection									
2	In feed									
3	In water									
4	Other									
mincat	Cat	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Injection</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>In feed</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>In water</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Injection	2	In feed	3	In water	4	Other
1	Injection									
2	In feed									
3	In water									
4	Other									

adminhorse	Horse	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Injection</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>In feed</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>In water</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Injection	2	In feed	3	In water	4	Other
1	Injection									
2	In feed									
3	In water									
4	Other									
adminonkey	Donkey	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Injection</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>In feed</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>In water</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Injection	2	In feed	3	In water	4	Other
1	Injection									
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adminchicken	Chicken	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Injection</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>In feed</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>In water</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Injection	2	In feed	3	In water	4	Other
1	Injection									
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adminother1	\${3}	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Injection</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>In feed</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>In water</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Injection	2	In feed	3	In water	4	Other
1	Injection									
2	In feed									
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adminother2	\${4}	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Injection</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>In feed</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>In water</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Injection	2	In feed	3	In water	4	Other
1	Injection									
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adminother3	\${5}	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Injection</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>In feed</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>In water</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Injection	2	In feed	3	In water	4	Other
1	Injection									
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3	In water									
4	Other									
grpAdminAntibioo	Hidden from user									
admincowo	Please specify how you have administered antibiotics to Cows in the last 6 months	User entered text								
adminpigo	Please specify how you have administered antibiotics to pigs in	User entered text								

	the last 6 months					
admisheepo	Please specify how you have administered antibiotics to sheep in the last 6 months	User entered text				
admingoato	Please specify how you have administered antibiotics to goats in the last 6 months	User entered text				
admindogo	Please specify how you have administered antibiotics to dogs in the last 6 months	User entered text				
admincato	Please specify how you have administered antibiotics to cats in the last 6 months	User entered text				
adminhorseo	Please specify how you have administered antibiotics to horses in the last 6 months	User entered text				
admindonkeyo	Please specify how you have administered antibiotics to donkeys in the last 6 months	User entered text				
adminchickeno	Please specify how you have administered antibiotics to chickens in the last 6 months	User entered text				
adminother1o	Please specify how you have administered antibiotics to \${3} in the last 6 months	User entered text				
adminother2o	Please specify how you have administered antibiotics to \${4} in the last 6 months	User entered text				
adminother3o	Please specify how you have administered antibiotics to \${5} in the last 6 months	User entered text				
abfeed	Do you add antibiotics to the feed of healthy animals?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
abf	Hidden from user					
generated_note_name_1541	Which animals do you add antibiotics to their food?	User entered text				
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_1542		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
abfeed0cow	Cow	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
abfeed0pig	Pig	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
abfeed0she	Sheep	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					

ab0feedgoa	Goat	1	Yes
		0	No
ab0feeddog	Dog	1	Yes
		0	No
abfeed0cat	Cat	1	Yes
		0	No
abfeed0hor	Horse	1	Yes
		0	No
abfeed0don	Donkey	1	Yes
		0	No
abfeed0chi	Chicken	1	Yes
		0	No
abfeed0oth1	#{3}	1	Yes
		0	No
abfeed0oth2	#{4}	1	Yes
		0	No
abfeed0oth3	#{5}	1	Yes
		0	No
af	Hidden from user		
co	Hidden from user		
abfeed0whycow	Why do you do this?	1	To increase the animal's growth
		2	To prevent disease when all the animals of the same species are well
		3	To prevent disease

		<table border="1"> <tr> <td></td> <td>when one animals of the same species is sick</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>		when one animals of the same species is sick	4	Other														
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4	Other																			
abfeed0diswhicow	If to treat a specific disease, which disease is this?	User entered text																		
adfeed0whecow	When was the last time this was done?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yesterday</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Once in the last week</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>In the last month</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Once in the last 6 months</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Less frequently than once in the last 6 months</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yesterday	2	Once in the last week	3	In the last month	4	Once in the last 6 months	5	Less frequently than once in the last 6 months								
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abfeed0anwhicow	Which antibiotics	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Tetracycline</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Streptomycin</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Ampicillin</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Amoxicillin-clavulanate</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Trimethoprim sulphonamide</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>Sulphonamide</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>Amoxicillin</td> </tr> <tr> <td>8</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> <tr> <td>11</td> <td>Unknown</td> </tr> </table>	1	Tetracycline	2	Streptomycin	3	Ampicillin	4	Amoxicillin-clavulanate	5	Trimethoprim sulphonamide	6	Sulphonamide	7	Amoxicillin	8	Other	11	Unknown
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7	Amoxicillin																			
8	Other																			
11	Unknown																			
abfeed0whycowo	Please specify why you add antibiotics to feed for cows	User entered text																		
abfeed0anwhicowo	Please specify other antibiotic	User entered text																		
p	Hidden from user																			
abfeed0whypig	Why do you do this?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>To increase the animal's growth</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>To prevent disease when all the animals of the same species are well</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>To prevent disease when one animals of the same species is sick</td> </tr> </table>	1	To increase the animal's growth	2	To prevent disease when all the animals of the same species are well	3	To prevent disease when one animals of the same species is sick												
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abfeed0diswhioth2	If to treat a specific disease, which disease is this?	User entered text																		
adfeed0wheoth2	When was the last time this was done?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yesterday</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Once in the last week</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>In the last month</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Once in the last 6 months</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Less frequently than once in the last 6 months</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yesterday	2	Once in the last week	3	In the last month	4	Once in the last 6 months	5	Less frequently than once in the last 6 months								
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abfeed0whyoth2o	Please specify why you add antibiotics to feed for \${4}	User entered text																		
abfeed0anwhioth2o	Please specify other antibiotic	User entered text																		
o3	Hidden from user																			
abfeed0whyoth3	If yes, why do you do this?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>To increase the animal's growth</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>To prevent disease when all the animals of the same species are well</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>To prevent disease when one animals of the same species is sick</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	To increase the animal's growth	2	To prevent disease when all the animals of the same species are well	3	To prevent disease when one animals of the same species is sick	4	Other										
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abfeed0whyoth3o	Please specify why you add antibiotics to feed for \${5}	User entered text																		
abfeed0anwhioth3o	Please specify other antibiotic	User entered text																		

abwat0	Do you add antibiotics to the water of healthy animals?	1	Yes
		0	No
aw	Hidden from user		
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_1655		1	Yes
		0	No
adwat0cow	Cow	1	Yes
		0	No
abwat0pig	Pig	1	Yes
		0	No
abwat0she	Sheep	1	Yes
		0	No
abwat0goa	Goat	1	Yes
		0	No
abwat0dog	Dog	1	Yes
		0	No
abwat0cat	Cat	1	Yes
		0	No
abwat0hor	Horse	1	Yes
		0	No
abwat0don	Donkey	1	Yes
		0	No
abwat0chi	Chicken	1	Yes
		0	No
abwat0another1	#{3}		

		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No						
1	Yes											
0	No											
abwat0another2	#{4}	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No						
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0	No											
ccw	Hidden from user											
abwat0whycow	If yes, why do you do this?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>To increase the animal's growth</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>To prevent disease when all the animals of the same species are well</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>To prevent disease when one animals of the same species is sick</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	To increase the animal's growth	2	To prevent disease when all the animals of the same species are well	3	To prevent disease when one animals of the same species is sick	4	Other		
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abwat0whycowo	Please specify why you add antibiotics to water for cows	User entered text														
abwat0anwhicowo	Please specify other antibiotic	User entered text														
pw	Hidden from user															
abwat0whypig	If yes, why do you do this?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>To increase the animal's growth</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>To prevent disease when all the animals of the same species are well</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>To prevent disease when one animals of the same species is sick</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	To increase the animal's growth	2	To prevent disease when all the animals of the same species are well	3	To prevent disease when one animals of the same species is sick	4	Other						
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abwat0anwhisheo	Please specify other antibiotic	User entered text																		
gw	Hidden from user																			
abwat0whygoa	If yes, why do you do this?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>To increase the animal's growth</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>To prevent disease when all the animals of the same species are well</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>To prevent disease when one animals of the same species is sick</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	To increase the animal's growth	2	To prevent disease when all the animals of the same species are well	3	To prevent disease when one animals of the same species is sick	4	Other										
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abwat0whygoao	Please specify why you add antibiotics to water for goats	User entered text																		
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dw	Hidden from user																			
abwat0whydog	If yes, why do you do this?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>To increase the animal's growth</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>To prevent disease when all the animals of the same species are well</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>To prevent disease when one animals of the same species is sick</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	To increase the animal's growth	2	To prevent disease when all the animals of the same species are well	3	To prevent disease when one animals of the same species is sick	4	Other										
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abwat0diswhidog	If to treat a specific disease, which disease is this?	User entered text																		
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adwat0whecat	When was the last time this was done?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yesterday</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Once in the last week</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>In the last month</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Once in the last 6 months</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Less frequently than once in the last 6 months</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yesterday	2	Once in the last week	3	In the last month	4	Once in the last 6 months	5	Less frequently than once in the last 6 months								
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needsam	When treating animals, do you use the same needle to administer injections?	User entered text																		
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needsamclcow	How do you clean the needle between cow injections?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td data-bbox="1190 215 1225 271">1</td> <td data-bbox="1225 215 1487 271">Do not clean</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1190 271 1225 327">2</td> <td data-bbox="1225 271 1487 327">Hold in flame</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1190 327 1225 427">3</td> <td data-bbox="1225 327 1487 427">Wash with soap and water</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1190 427 1225 528">4</td> <td data-bbox="1225 427 1487 528">Discard and use a clean needle</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1190 528 1225 584">5</td> <td data-bbox="1225 528 1487 584">Wash in alcohol</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1190 584 1225 640">6</td> <td data-bbox="1225 584 1487 640">Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	Do not clean	2	Hold in flame	3	Wash with soap and water	4	Discard and use a clean needle	5	Wash in alcohol	6	Other
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4	Discard and use a clean needle													
5	Wash in alcohol													
6	Other													
needsamclpig	How do you clean the needle between pig injections?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td data-bbox="1190 701 1225 757">1</td> <td data-bbox="1225 701 1487 757">Do not clean</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1190 757 1225 813">2</td> <td data-bbox="1225 757 1487 813">Hold in flame</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1190 813 1225 913">3</td> <td data-bbox="1225 813 1487 913">Wash with soap and water</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1190 913 1225 1014">4</td> <td data-bbox="1225 913 1487 1014">Discard and use a clean needle</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1190 1014 1225 1070">5</td> <td data-bbox="1225 1014 1487 1070">Wash in alcohol</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1190 1070 1225 1126">6</td> <td data-bbox="1225 1070 1487 1126">Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	Do not clean	2	Hold in flame	3	Wash with soap and water	4	Discard and use a clean needle	5	Wash in alcohol	6	Other
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needsamclshe	How do you clean the needle between sheep injections?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td data-bbox="1190 1187 1225 1243">1</td> <td data-bbox="1225 1187 1487 1243">Do not clean</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1190 1243 1225 1299">2</td> <td data-bbox="1225 1243 1487 1299">Hold in flame</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1190 1299 1225 1400">3</td> <td data-bbox="1225 1299 1487 1400">Wash with soap and water</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1190 1400 1225 1500">4</td> <td data-bbox="1225 1400 1487 1500">Discard and use a clean needle</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1190 1500 1225 1556">5</td> <td data-bbox="1225 1500 1487 1556">Wash in alcohol</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1190 1556 1225 1612">6</td> <td data-bbox="1225 1556 1487 1612">Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	Do not clean	2	Hold in flame	3	Wash with soap and water	4	Discard and use a clean needle	5	Wash in alcohol	6	Other
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needsamclgoa	How do you clean the needle between goat injections?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td data-bbox="1190 1673 1225 1729">1</td> <td data-bbox="1225 1673 1487 1729">Do not clean</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1190 1729 1225 1785">2</td> <td data-bbox="1225 1729 1487 1785">Hold in flame</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1190 1785 1225 1886">3</td> <td data-bbox="1225 1785 1487 1886">Wash with soap and water</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1190 1886 1225 1986">4</td> <td data-bbox="1225 1886 1487 1986">Discard and use a clean needle</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1190 1986 1225 2042">5</td> <td data-bbox="1225 1986 1487 2042">Wash in alcohol</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1190 2042 1225 2098">6</td> <td data-bbox="1225 2042 1487 2098">Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	Do not clean	2	Hold in flame	3	Wash with soap and water	4	Discard and use a clean needle	5	Wash in alcohol	6	Other
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needsamcldog	How do you clean the needle between dog injections?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Do not clean</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Hold in flame</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Wash with soap and water</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Discard and use a clean needle</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Wash in alcohol</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Do not clean	2	Hold in flame	3	Wash with soap and water	4	Discard and use a clean needle	5	Wash in alcohol	6	Other
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needsamclcat	How do you clean the needle between cat injections?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Do not clean</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Hold in flame</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Wash with soap and water</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Discard and use a clean needle</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Wash in alcohol</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Do not clean	2	Hold in flame	3	Wash with soap and water	4	Discard and use a clean needle	5	Wash in alcohol	6	Other
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needsamclhor	How do you clean the needle between horse injections?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Do not clean</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Hold in flame</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Wash with soap and water</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Discard and use a clean needle</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Wash in alcohol</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Do not clean	2	Hold in flame	3	Wash with soap and water	4	Discard and use a clean needle	5	Wash in alcohol	6	Other
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needsamcldon	How do you clean the needle between donkey injections?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Do not clean</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Hold in flame</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Wash with soap and water</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Discard and use a clean needle</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Wash in alcohol</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Do not clean	2	Hold in flame	3	Wash with soap and water	4	Discard and use a clean needle	5	Wash in alcohol	6	Other
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needsamclchi	How do you clean the needle between chicken injections?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Do not clean</td></tr> </table>	1	Do not clean										
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needsamcloth1	How do you clean the needle between \${3} injections?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Do not clean</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Hold in flame</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Wash with soap and water</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Discard and use a clean needle</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Wash in alcohol</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Do not clean	2	Hold in flame	3	Wash with soap and water	4	Discard and use a clean needle	5	Wash in alcohol	6	Other
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needsamcloth2	How do you clean the needle between \${4} injections?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Do not clean</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Hold in flame</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Wash with soap and water</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Discard and use a clean needle</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Wash in alcohol</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Do not clean	2	Hold in flame	3	Wash with soap and water	4	Discard and use a clean needle	5	Wash in alcohol	6	Other
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needsamcloth3	How do you clean the needle between \${5} injections?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Do not clean</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Hold in flame</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Wash with soap and water</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Discard and use a clean needle</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Wash in alcohol</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Do not clean	2	Hold in flame	3	Wash with soap and water	4	Discard and use a clean needle	5	Wash in alcohol	6	Other
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note_end	You have completed data collection for this participant. On the next screen please remember to: 1. Verify that 'Mark form as	User entered text												

	finalized' is ticked 2. Click 'Save Form and Exit'	
init_staff	Staff initials	User entered text
calc_sinit	Hidden from user	
generated_note_name_1801	The provided staff initials: \${9} are not valid. Please navigate back and provide valid staff initials.	User entered text
meta	Hidden from user	
instanceID	Hidden from user	
instanceName	Hidden from user	